

Maiden Issue

IILM LAWJOURNAL

Volume I, Issue 1, 2023

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IILM UNIVERSITY

Greater Noida, (INDIA)

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IILM UNIVERSITY
Knowledge Park-II,
Greater Noida
(INDIA)

This volume should be cited as: *Vol. I, IILMLJ Issue1,2023*

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Published By: ILM School of Law, IILM University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India

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EDITORIAL

It is a matter of immense pleasure to put the maiden issue of the *IILM Law Journal*, April 2023 in the hands of our respectful and responsive members of the legal Fraternity. As a new initiative, it is to provide opportunity to law researchers and those who are doing research in allied subjects, to publish their research, after *peer reviewing*, for the benefit of people interested in legal studies, social studies, legislation, judicial decisions and working of the law. The journal is expected to emerge as a vehicle for thought transmission in multiple dimensions across disciplines and sharing of concerns with critical thinking. Original focused studies with purpose, after appropriate choice of methodology, in preference to stereotypes, will be highly appreciated.

Researches for exploring traditional wisdom and historical context, scientific enquiry, apposite scrutiny and futuristic outlook will be a priority for this journal. Case comments, research notes, review articles, rejoinders and book reviews will be highly appreciated.

This maiden issue covers entries on the themes: Indian Constitutional Stance and Achievements on United Nations Sustainable Development Goals of Equality And Justice; Indian Approach to International Arbitration; India's Target to be a Carbo-Free Country; Data Protection vis-a-vis Right to Privacy In India; Medical Tourism and the Law in India; Collective Investment Scheme; Role of Judiciary in Prevention of Custodial Death with Special Reference to Human Right Jurisprudence; Enforceability of Non-Compete Covenants in Employment Contracts vis-a-vis Judicial Pronouncements in India, and the Movement of Criminal Law towards Equality and Justice for All Regardless of Gender. These are providing ideas for national development, international understanding, working of law in society, policy framing, legislation, judging, public administration, diplomacy, system-

management, regulation of technology and social reform. I wish the journal to contribute to Indian Jurisprudence as a rich platform for projection of well researched factual situations and viable ideas and suggestions.

I am grateful to the contributors, advisors, reviewers and the members of the editorial committee of the journal for their efforts cooperation in bringing out this issue of the journal in a shortest possible period of time. Further, critical comments and constructive suggestions from any one for improvement are most welcome.

Thanks.

Prof. M. Afzal Wani
Editor

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INDIAN CONSTITUTIONAL STANCE AND ACHIEVEMENTS ON UNITED NATIONS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS OF EQUALITY AND JUSTICE

Prof. M. Afzal Wani*

Abstract

World is a good place to live together for all human beings with peace and harmony, maintain at the same time a sustainable relationship with planet earth itself and all it possesses for generations. How consciously the People of the United Nations are carefully and dutifully living of this planet with concern and cooperation needs a consistent evaluation. The United Nations Millennium Development Goals in 2000 and the Sustainable Development Goals in 2015 demand a frequent review and appropriate action to promote a world with no poverty; zero hunger; good health and well being; quality education; gender equality; clean water and sanitation; affordable and clean energy; decent work and economic growth; industry, innovation and infrastructure; reduced inequality; sustainable cities and communities; responsible consumption and production; climate action; life below water; life on land; peace and justice strong institutions; and partnerships to achieve the goals. This article after seven and a half years declaration of Sustainable Development Goals gives review of the agenda and visible results so far based on data available in the public domain.

Key Words: SDGs, understanding, achievements and required appropriate action.

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I-The UNSustainable Development Goals

Development is presently at the centre of all human endeavours; but, the development itself demands putting people at the centre of development, of course, with due sustainability. At UN, The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), launched in 1990, the Human Development Report, with the goal of putting people actually at the center of the development process in terms of economic debate, policy and advocacy. The report is an independent report commissioned by the UNDP, which is a product of a selected team of leading scholars, development practitioners and members of the UNDP. Continuing the process, in September 2000, building upon a decade of major United Nations conferences and summits, world leaders came together at United Nations Headquarters in New York to adopt the United Nations Millennium Declaration, committing their nations to a new global partnership to reduce extreme poverty and setting out a series of time-bound targets—with a deadline of 2015—that have become known as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).¹ United Nations Secretary-General BAN Ki-moon said, “Eradicating extreme poverty continues to be one of the main challenges of our time, and is a major concern of the international community. Ending this scourge will require the combined efforts of all, governments, civil society organizations and the private sector, in the context of a stronger and more effective global partnership for development. The Millennium Development Goals set time bound targets, by which progress in reducing income poverty, hunger, disease, lack of adequate shelter and exclusion — while promoting gender equality, health, education and environmental sustainability—can be measured. They also embody basic human rights — the rights of each person on the planet to health, education, shelter and security. The Goals are ambitious but feasible and, together with the comprehensive United Nations development agenda, set the course for the world’s efforts to alleviate extreme poverty by 2015.” All that through now much more remain to be done and achieved.

1. <https://www.un.org/millenniumgoals/bkgd.shtml#:~:text=The%20Millennium%20Development%20>

Think of the world in 2030, fully inclusive of persons of all colours, castes, classes, creeds, genders, abilities, languages and regions, living together with peace, harmony and happiness. On 25th September 2015, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the '2030- Agenda' for Sustainable Development that includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Building on the principle of "leaving no one behind", the '2030-Agenda' accentuates a holistic approach to achieving sustainable development for all.

The 17 sustainable development goals (SDGs) to transform our world are: No Poverty, Zero Hunger, Good Health and Well-being, Quality Education, Gender Equality, Clean Water and Sanitation, Affordable and Clean Energy, Decent Work and Economic Growth, Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure, Reduced Inequality, Sustainable Cities and Communities, Responsible Consumption and Production, Climate Action, Life below Water, Life on Land, Peace and Justice and Strong Institutions.²

Foreseeing Reduction in Inequality

☞ The Goal 10 providing for reducing inequality within and among countries is about assuring at least by 2030 to:

- a) progressively achieve and sustain income growth of the bottom 40 per cent of the population at a rate higher than the national average;

2. GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goals-

GOAL 1: No Poverty; GOAL 2: Zero Hunger; GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being; 4: Quality Education; GOAL 5: Gender Equality; GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation; GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy; GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth; GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure; GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality; GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities; GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production; GOAL 13: Climate Action; GOAL 14: Life below Water; GOAL 15: Life on Land; GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions; GOAL 17: Partnerships to achieve the Goals.

- b) empower and promote the social, economic and political inclusion of all, irrespective of age, sex, disability, race, ethnicity, origin, religion or economic or other status;
- c) ensure equal opportunity and reduce inequalities of outcome, including by eliminating discriminatory laws, policies and practices and promoting appropriate legislation, policies and action in this regard;
- d) Adopt policies, especially fiscal, wage and social protection policies, and progressively achieve greater equality;
- e) Improve the regulation and monitoring of global financial markets and institutions and strengthen the implementation of such regulations;
- f) Ensure enhanced representation and voice for developing countries in decision-making in global international economic and financial institutions in order to deliver more effective, credible, accountable and legitimate institutions;
- g) Facilitate orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility of people, including through the implementation of planned and well-managed migration policies;
- h) Implement the principle of special and differential treatment for developing countries, in particular least developed countries, in accordance with World Trade Organization agreements;
- i) Encourage official development assistance and financial flows, including foreign direct investment, to States where the need is greatest, in particular least developed countries, African countries, small island developing States and landlocked developing countries, in accordance with their national plans and programmes;

- j) reduce to less than 3 per cent the transaction costs of migrant remittances and eliminate remittance corridors with costs higher than 5 per cent.

Promotion of Peaceful Societies, Sustainability and Access to Justice

Goal 16. Seeks to promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all and build effective, accountable and inclusive institutions at all levels. The objective is to-

- a) significantly reduce all forms of violence and related death rates everywhere;
- b) end abuse, exploitation, trafficking and all forms of violence against and torture of children
- c) promote the rule of law at the national and international levels and ensure equal access to justice for all;
- d) significantly reduce illicit financial and arms flows, strengthen the recovery and return of stolen assets and combat all forms of organized crime;
- e) substantially reduce corruption and bribery in all their forms;
- f) develop effective, accountable and transparent institutions at all levels;
- g) ensure responsive, inclusive, participatory and representative decision-making at all levels
- h) broaden and strengthen the participation of developing countries in the institutions of global governance;
- i) provide legal identity for all, including birth registration;
- j) ensure public access to information and protect fundamental freedoms, in accordance with national legislation and international agreements;

- k) strengthen relevant national institutions, including through international cooperation, for building capacity at all levels, in particular in developing countries, to prevent violence and combat terrorism and crime; and
- l) promote and enforce non-discriminatory laws and policies for sustainable development.

SDGs and the UN Charter

These sustainable development goals are basically action to carry forward the main agenda set by the United Nations in its Charter and later resolutions from time to time about promoting better conditions of life for all people to live with dignity. In its Preamble the Charter of the United Nations (1945) asserts that the people of the United Nations are determined to: “to save succeeding generations from the scourge of war, which twice in our life-time has brought untold sorrow to mankind, and to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person, in the equal rights of men and women and of nations large and small, and to establish conditions under which justice and respect for the obligations arising from treaties and other sources of international law can be maintained, and to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom”. And to accomplish these ends, they are resolved to combine efforts: “to practice tolerance and live together in peace with one another as good neighbors, and to unite our strength to maintain international peace and security, and to ensure, by the acceptance of principles and the institution of methods, that armed force shall not be used, save in the common interest, and to employ international machinery for the promotion of the economic and social advancement of all peoples. Article I of the Charter lays down the following as its objectives:

- 1) To maintain international peace and security, and to that end: to take effective collective measures for the prevention and removal of threats to the peace, and for the suppression of acts of aggression or other breaches

of the peace, and to bring about by peaceful means, and in conformity with the principles of justice and international law, adjustment or settlement of inter-national disputes or situations which might lead to a breach of the peace;

- 2) To develop friendly relations among nations based on respect for the principle of equal rights and self-determination of peoples, and to take other appropriate measures to strengthen universal peace;
- 3) To achieve international cooperation in solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural, or humanitarian character, and in promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and for fundamental freedoms for all without distinction as to race, sex, language, or religion; and
- 4) To be a center for harmonizing the actions of nations in the attainment of these common ends.

Universal Declaration of Human Rights and SDGs

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) (1948) in its Preamble, with due eloquence, sets forth the universally significant assumptions that: the recognition of the inherent dignity and of the equal and inalienable rights of all members of the human family is the foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world; disregard and contempt for human rights have resulted in barbarous acts which have outraged the conscience of mankind, and the advent of a world in which human beings shall enjoy freedom of speech and belief and freedom from fear and want has been proclaimed as the highest aspiration of the common people; and man is not to be compelled to have recourse to rebellion against tyranny and oppression as the human rights should be protected by the rule of law. The United Nations have in the Charter reaffirmed their faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person and in the equal rights of men and women and have

determined to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom. It has been considered essential to promote the development of friendly relations between nations and co-operation for the promotion of universal respect for and observance of human rights and fundamental freedoms. It proclaimed UDHR as a common standard of achievement for all peoples and all nations, to the end that every individual and every organ of society, keeping this declaration constantly in mind, shall strive by teaching and education to promote respect for these rights and freedoms and by progressive measures, national and international, to secure their universal and effective recognition and observance, both among the peoples of Member States themselves and among the peoples of territories under their jurisdiction.

The notably most significant human rights which need to be religiously advanced by governments in all nation states are: All human beings are born free and equal in dignity and rights. They are endowed with reason and conscience and should act towards one another in a spirit of brotherhood.³ Everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs, whether it be independent, trust, non-self-governing or under any other limitation of sovereignty.⁴ Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.⁵ No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms.⁶ No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading

³ Article 1

⁴ Article 2

⁵ Article 3

⁶ Article 4, 5, 6

treatment or punishment.⁷ Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law.⁸ All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination.⁹ Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law.¹⁰ No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile.¹¹ Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.¹²

II-India's Constitutional Stance on SDGs *Equalization and Equal Opportunities*

Article 14 of the Constitution of India provides the “State shall not deny to any person equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws within the territory of India”. It restricts all possible forms of denial of equality to any citizen or non-citizen and expressly strengthens the guarantees of ‘equality before law’ and equal protection of law’. It clearly hits out at any form of discrimination and arbitrariness which is reported frequently in countries with conflicting groups. The societies with distinctions of social peace are a dream of the United Nations for peace within and among countries which the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, 1948 and various national constitutions must follow as the priority for attaining peace and sustainable development. All countries with

⁷. Article 7

⁸. Preamble, UDHR, 1948.

⁹. Ibid

¹⁰ Article 8

¹¹ Article 9

¹² Article 10

poor human rights record need to do more for attaining better level of equality and divorce the activities leading to enhanced inequality.

To carry out the agenda of sustainability, the Constitution of India contains more provisions to make possible attainment of equality in regard to the diverse society in the country. Article 15 prohibits discrimination on grounds of religion, race, caste, sex or place of birth stating that the “State shall not discriminate against any citizen on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them, and no citizen shall, on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, place of birth or any of them, be subject to any disability, liability, restriction or condition with regard to— (a) access to shops, public restaurants, hotels and places of public entertainment; or (b) the use of wells, tanks, bathing *ghats*, roads and places of public resort maintained wholly or partly out of State funds or dedicated to the use of the general public. However, in this article the State shall not be prevented from making any special provision for women and children because of their traditionally exposed social and economic position in Indian society. Also the State can make any special provision for the advancement of any socially and educationally backward classes of citizens or for the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes. The state shall, however, have the power to make any special provision, by law, for the advancement of any socially and educationally backward classes of citizens or for the Scheduled Castes or the Scheduled Tribes in so far as such special provisions relate to their admission to educational institutions including private educational institutions, whether aided or unaided by the State, *other than the minority educational institutions*¹³. The State can also make any special provision for the advancement of any other economically weaker sections of citizens. Any special provision can also be made for the advancement of any other economically weaker sections of citizens

¹³ As referred to in clause (1) of article 30.

in so far as such special provisions relate to their admission to educational institutions including private educational institutions, whether aided or unaided by the State, but not to minority educational institutions, which in the case of reservation would be in addition to the existing reservations and subject to a maximum of ten per cent of the total seats in each category.¹⁴

Equality in matters of public employment

Article 16 provides that there shall be equality of opportunity for all citizens in matters relating to employment or appointment to any office under the State. No citizen shall be ineligible for, or discriminated against in respect of, any employment or office under the State on grounds only of religion, race, caste, sex, descent, place of birth, residence or any of them. The Parliament may make any law prescribing, in regard to a class or classes of employment or appointment to an office under the Government of, or any local or other authority within, a State or Union territory, any requirement as to residence within that State or Union territory prior to such employment or appointment.

The Parliament is, in spite of that provision, empowered to make any provision for the reservation of appointments or posts in favour of any backward class of citizens which, in the opinion of the State, is not adequately represented in the services under the State. Similarly, the State can make any provision for reservation in matters of promotion, with consequential seniority, to any class or classes of posts in the services under the State in favour of the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes which, in the opinion of the State, are not adequately represented in the services under the State. The State may consider any unfilled vacancies of a year which were so reserved for being filled up in that year as a separate

¹⁴ For the purposes of this article and article 16, “economically weaker sections” shall be such as may be notified by the State from time to time on the basis of family income and other indicators of economic disadvantage.

class of vacancies to be filled up in any succeeding year or years and such class of vacancies shall not be considered together with the vacancies of the year in which they are being filled up for determining the ceiling of fifty per cent. reservation on total number of vacancies of that year.

This article shall not affect the operation of any law which provides that the incumbent of an office in connection with the affairs of any religious or denominational institution or any member of the governing body thereof shall be a person professing a particular religion or belonging to a particular denomination.

After seven decades of constitutional experience the State has been empowered from making any provision for the reservation of appointments or posts in favour of any economically weaker sections of citizens other than the already mentioned classes, in addition to the existing reservation and subject to a maximum of ten per cent of the posts in each category.

A major step was taken by the constitution makers about reducing inequality was insertion of article 17 in the Constitution of India, which abolished untouchability and for badeits practice in any form. It made enforcement of any disability arising out of untouchability an offence punishable in accordance with law.

Basic Freedoms for All

Article 19 of the Constitution of India guarantees basic freedoms to all the citizens overriding all customary taboos. It provides:

All citizens shall have the right—

- (a) to freedom of speech and expression;
- (b) to assemble peaceably and without arms;
- (c) to form associations or unions;
- (d) to move freely throughout the territory of India;

- (e) to reside and settle in any part of the territory of India;
- (g) to practice any profession, or to carry on any occupation, trade or business.

This constitutional measure is extremely important for ensuring a great role as well as benefit under the Sustainable Development Goals.

Education for All

Article 21A of the constitution declares right to education as fundamental right, making the State bound to provide free and compulsory education to all children of the age of six to fourteen years in such manner as the State may, by law, determine.

Through Directive Principles of State Policy, the State is under an obligation to endeavour to provide early childhood care and education for all children until they complete the age of six years;¹⁵ and promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and, in particular, of the Scheduled Castes and the Scheduled Tribes, and shall protect them from social injustice and all forms of exploitation.¹⁶

No Exploitation for Anyone

The Constitution of India prohibits exploitation in the form it prevailed for long in the country. Traffic in human beings and *beggar* and other similar forms of forced labour are prohibited and any contravention of this provision is an offence punishable in accordance with law. The State can, but, impose compulsory service for public purposes, though in imposing such service the State shall not make any discrimination on grounds only of religion, race, caste or class or any of them.¹⁷ No child below the age of

¹⁵ Article 45.

¹⁶ Article 46.

¹⁷ Article 23, Constitution of India, 1950.

fourteen years is allowed to be employed to work in any factory or mine or engaged in any other hazardous employment.¹⁸ A special enactment is dealing with the regulation of labour by children, namely the Child Labour (Prohibition and Regulation) Act, 1986. It contains detailed provisions against exploitation of children in terms of age, nature of work, leisure, educational opportunities and other related matters.

Freedom of Conscience for All

To ensure equality and well being, the Constitution of India guarantees that all persons are equally entitled to freedom of conscience and the right freely to profess, practise and propagate religion. The State can only make law for (a) regulating or restricting any economic, financial, political or other secular activity which may be associated with religious practice; and (b) to provide for social welfare and reform or to throw open of Hindu religious institutions of a public character to all classes and sections of Hindus.¹⁹ Every religious denomination or any section thereof shall have the right— (a) to establish and maintain institutions for religious and charitable purposes; (b) to manage its own affairs in matters of religion; (c) to own and acquire movable and immovable property; and (d) to administer such property in accordance with law.²⁰ Giving freedom as to payment of taxes for promotion of any particular religion, it is provided that no person shall be compelled to pay any taxes, the proceeds of which are specifically appropriated in payment of expenses for the promotion or maintenance of any particular religion or religious

¹⁸ Article 24.

¹⁹ There are two Explanations in this regard. Explanation I.—The wearing and carrying of kirpans shall be deemed to be included in the profession of the Sikh religion. Explanation II...the reference to Hindus shall be construed as including a reference to persons professing the Sikh, Jain or Buddhist religion, and the reference to Hindu religious institutions shall be construed accordingly.

²⁰ Article 26.

denomination.²¹ Article 28 regulates the matters related to freedom as to attendance at religious instruction or religious worship in certain educational institutions. It enjoins that any religious instruction shall not be provided in any educational institution wholly maintained out of State funds, though can be in an educational institution which is administered by the State but has been established under any endowment or trust which requires that religious instruction shall be imparted in such institution. As regards individuals, no person “attending any educational institution recognised by the State or receiving aid out of State funds shall be required to take part in any religious instruction that may be imparted in such institution or to attend any religious worship that may be conducted in such institution or in any premises attached thereto unless such person or, if such person is a minor, his guardian has given his consent thereto”. The individual choice to maintain his way of life and thought is expressly recognized.

Universal Cultural Sustainability

Article 29 of the Constitution of India provides that any section of the citizens residing in the territory of India or any part thereof having a distinct language, script or culture of its own shall have the right to conserve the same.²² Any citizen cannot be denied admission into any educational institution maintained by the State or receiving aid out of State funds on grounds only of religion, race, caste, language or any of them.²³ To ensure a sustainable march in the main stream for all cultural groups and faiths, article 30 of the Constitution of India enables all minorities, whether based on religion or language, a right to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice. For further protection, article 30 requires that in making any law providing for the compulsory

²¹ Article 27.

²² Article 29 (1)

²³ Article 20 (2)

acquisition of any property of an educational institution established and administered by a minority, the State shall ensure that the amount fixed by or determined under such law for the acquisition of such property is such as would not restrict or abrogate the right guaranteed so “to establish and administer educational institutions of their choice”.²⁴ The State shall not, in granting aid to educational institutions, discriminate against any educational institution on the ground that it is under the management of a minority, whether based on religion or language.²⁵

Judicial Assurance and Assertion

To make the attainment of all these constitutional targets/rights most probable, ‘Right to Constitutional Remedies’ for enforcement of these rights has been conferred by article 32 of the constitution giving right to move the Supreme Court of India directly by appropriate proceedings for the enforcement of the rights conferred leading to attainment of these goals. The Supreme Court has power to issue directions or orders or writs, including writs in the nature of *habeas corpus*, *mandamus*, *prohibition*, *quo warranto* and *certiorari*, whichever may be appropriate. Additionally, the Parliament may by law empower any other court to exercise within the local limits of its jurisdiction all or any of these powers exercisable by the Supreme Court. Keeping in view the significance of these assured entitlements, the right guaranteed for seeking the remedy from the Supreme Court cannot be suspended except as otherwise may be provided for by this Constitution.

III-Constitutional Directives to the State and SDGs

Just Social Order with Equality

Article 38 of the Constitution of India directs the State to secure a social order for the promotion of welfare of the people by striving to promote the welfare of the people by securing and protecting as

²⁴ Article 30 (1A).

²⁵ Article 30 (2)

effectively as it may a *social order in which justice, social, economic and political, shall inform all the institutions of the national life.*²⁶ In relation to ‘equality’ the State is directed, in particular, to strive to minimise the inequalities in income, and endeavour to eliminate inequalities in status, facilities and opportunities, not only amongst individuals but also amongst groups of people residing in different areas or engaged in different vocations.²⁷

The State has been directed to follow certain policies towards securing—

- a) that the citizens, men and women equally, have the right to an adequate means of livelihood;
- b) that the ownership and control of the material resources of the community are so distributed as best to subserve the common good;
- c) that the operation of the economic system does not result in the concentration of wealth and means of production to the common detriment;
- d) that there is equal pay for equal work for both men and women;
- e) that the health and strength of workers, men and women, and the tender age of children are not abused and that citizens are not forced by economic necessity to enter avocations unsuited to their age or strength;
- f) that children are given opportunities and facilities to develop in a healthy manner and in conditions of freedom and dignity and that childhood and youth are protected against exploitation and against moral and material abandonment.²⁸

²⁶ Article 38 (1); emphasis is added.

²⁷ Article 38 (2).

²⁸ Article 39.

Equal Justice and Free Legal Aid

The State has been directed to secure that the operation of the legal system promotes justice, on a basis of equal opportunity, and shall, in particular, provide free legal aid, by suitable legislation or schemes or in any other way, to ensure that opportunities for securing justice are not denied to any citizen by reason of economic or other disabilities.²⁹

Sustainable Operational Conditions

The Constitution of India requires the State, within the limits of its economic capacity and development, make effective provision for securing the right to work, to education and to public assistance in cases of unemployment, old age, sickness and disablement, and in other cases of undeserved want.³⁰ The State should make provision for securing just and humane conditions of work and for maternity relief.³¹ Also, the State should endeavour to secure, by suitable legislation or economic organisation or in any other way, to all workers, agricultural, industrial or otherwise, work, a living wage, conditions of work ensuring a decent standard of life and full enjoyment of leisure and social and cultural opportunities and, in particular, the State shall endeavour to promote cottage industries on an individual or co-operative basis in rural areas.³²

The State has been enjoined to make possible more inclusion of people into industry by suitable legislation or in any other way, for securing the participation of workers in the management of undertakings, establishments or other organisations engaged in any industry.³³ The State should likewise endeavour to promote voluntary formation, autonomous functioning, democratic control and professional management of co-operative societies.³⁴

²⁹ Article 39 A.

³⁰ Article 41.

³¹ Article 42.

³² Article 43.

³³ Article 43A

³⁴ Article 43B

Standard of Living and Improvement in Public Health

The State shall regard the raising of the level of nutrition and the standard of living of its people and the improvement of public health as among its primary duties and, in particular, the State shall endeavour to bring about prohibition of the consumption except for medicinal purposes of intoxicating drinks and of drugs which are injurious to health.³⁵ The responsibility of the State includes organization of agriculture and animal husbandry on modern and scientific lines and shall, in particular, take steps for preserving and improving the breeds, and prohibiting the slaughter, of cows and calves and other milch and draught cattle;³⁶ to protect and improve the environment and to safeguard the forests and wild life of the country;³⁷ and to protect every monument or place or object of artistic or historic interest, declared by or under law made by Parliament to be of national importance, from spoliation, disfigurement, destruction, removal, disposal or export, as the case may be.³⁸

Article 50 directs the State to take steps to separate the judiciary from the executive in the public services of the State. The provision needs much attention for ensuring the independent and fair performance by the judiciary to enrich well being of the people of India escaping executive interferences.

Promotion of International Peace and Security

The State, under article 51 of the Constitution of India, is under an obligation to endeavour to:

- a) promote international peace and security;
- b) maintain just and honourable relations between nations;
- c) foster respect for international law and treaty obligations in

³⁵ Article 47.

³⁶ Article 48.

³⁷ Article 48A

³⁸ Article 49

- the dealings of organised peoples with one another; and
- d) encourage settlement of international disputes by arbitration.

Fundamental Duties

Under article 51 of the Constitution of India, it is the duty of every citizen of India:

- a) to abide by the Constitution and respect its ideals and institutions;³⁹
- b) to promote harmony and the spirit of common brotherhood amongst all the people of India transcending religious, linguistic and regional or sectional diversities; to renounce practices derogatory to the dignity of women;⁴⁰
- c) to value and preserve the rich heritage of our composite culture;⁴¹
- d) to protect and improve the natural environment including forests, lakes, rivers and wild life, and to have compassion for living creatures;⁴²
- e) to develop the scientific temper, humanism and the spirit of inquiry and reform;⁴³
- f) to safeguard public property and to abjure violence;⁴⁴
- g) to strive towards excellence in all spheres of individual and collective activity so that the nation constantly rises to higher levels of endeavour and achievement;⁴⁵

³⁹ Article 51A (a)

⁴⁰ Article 51A (e)

⁴¹ Article 51A (f)

⁴² Article 51A (g)

⁴³ Article 51A (h)

⁴⁴ Article 51A (i)

⁴⁵ Article 51A (j)

- h) who is a parent or guardian to provide opportunities for education to his child or, as the case may be, ward between the age of six and fourteen years.⁴⁶

IV-Status Reports on Achievements So Far

Global Scene

The United Nations adopted the Sustainable Development Goals as a pledge to end poverty, hunger, illiteracy, address water shortages, eliminate inequalities and focus on the climate, peace and justice through national and international cooperation. Goals set as a 15-year timeline to meet certain human and environmental challenges by 2030. The United Nations Member States adopted the Sustainable Development Goals as a commitment to end poverty, improve education, address water shortages, eliminate inequalities and focus on the climate, among 17 designated targets. Seven years have passed since the creation of the Agenda and in that time political, natural, human and economic factors have weighed heavily on the success of the SDGs. Part of the original plan was accountability through annual reporting. The Sustainable Development Goals Report is compiled by the U.N. Department of Economic and Social Affairs, with input from international and regional organizations, the UN system of agencies, statisticians and industry professionals. The 2022 report was released earlier with results not satisfactory. “Efforts to end poverty have been reversed by four years, mostly as a result of the pandemic. Job losses created an economic impact while inflation is still making it more difficult to stretch the budget. Efforts to end hunger have equally been affected by war, rising food prices and systematic inequalities. About one in ten humans suffer from hunger while one in three lacks access to food. The pandemic delivered a crushing hit on world health with over 500 million infections and 15 million related deaths. The disruption in health services contributed to a lack of preventative care, which means death rates rose from other causes,

⁴⁶ Article 51A(k)

and the overall life expectancy dropped globally. The pandemic caused a breakdown in learning that will be seen for at least a generation. Many students will never return to school. Meanwhile, in low-income areas, the inequalities of access to education and educational tools have dropped, widening the inequality gap.

The pandemic also affected the role women play in the workplace, with more mothers leaving jobs to stay home with children compared to men. About 57% of women are making their own informed medical decisions. Over one in four women have reported abuse by a partner. Even with a seven-year increase, women only represent around 26% of political leadership jobs. Also, human activity over the past 300 years has wiped out 85% of the planet's wetland areas. Over 3 billion people have a questionable water supply. Over 744 million people live in a country with water concerns. The report concludes we need to multiply current efforts by a four-time increase to meet water goals for 2030.

Inflation, changing employment environments and supply chain issues continue to result in higher than pre-pandemic unemployment rates and poor economic conditions.

Manufacturing has mostly rebounded from the pandemic, with the exception of least developed countries where an increased inequality is seen. However, jobs within manufacturing have dropped by about one-third. Small businesses are still struggling to produce a profit and have adequate access to loans.

World events have caused a dynamic rift in equality between countries while refugees, migrant deaths and discrimination are all high.

Plans for disaster risk have nearly doubled in the past seven years while increasing populations have created mounting waste problems. Public transportation is highly inconsistent globally and,

according to WHO, 99% of the world's urban population is dealing with air pollution.

Food waste is a growing issue at both the agricultural and consumer level. North America and Europe are recycling nearly 48% of electronic waste while much of the developing world recycles less than 2%. As for consumption, we're relying on natural resources more than ever and practicing unsustainable patterns of product consumption.

Damage to coral reefs, melting glacier ice, sea level rise, drought, rising global temperatures and natural disasters are all in the forecast in the short and long term without drastic change. Last year, 2021 saw the highest energy-related carbon emissions ever recorded.

The ocean is a carbon sink, which can be a good thing for air breathers. However, it's catastrophic for marine animals. Ocean warming, plastic pollution and over fishing add insult to injury.

Crops and livestock are responsible for 90% of the world's deforestation. Around 40,000 species are in threat of extinction in the next 40 years. Biodiversity has taken a huge hit during the pandemic with priority to people and the economy. In a bit of good news, nearly half of biodiversity areas are now being protected.

Violent conflicts are increasing on a global and local level with one-quarter of the population living in conflict-affected areas. On a positive note, global homicides dropped in the first five years of the SDGs, however, one-third of the population reports being scared to walk alone at night, even in their own neighborhood.

This is the one area of the report where significant progress was seen. Development assistance reached a new high thanks to pandemic aid. Foreign investments and remittances both

rebounded. Internet access and usage have increased, too. However, developing countries saw a significant increase in debt during the same time period.”

The report is alarming. Achieving the goals will require a synchronized global effort.⁴⁷

Indian Scene

Starvation

In the 2022 Global Hunger Index, India ranks 107th out of the 121 countries with sufficient data to calculate 2022 GHI scores. With a score of 29.1, India has a level of hunger that is serious.⁴⁸ Concerns have grown in India over hunger deaths, food aid, and data gaps. The government is accused of failing to log starvation deaths, while the safety net is not catching all it should. Shocking stories are being shared on the situation.⁴⁹

About one starvation death it is reported, “In the weeks before he died in India’s West Bengal in August, 30-year-old migrant worker Sanjoy Sardar rarely ate more than one meal a day.⁵⁰ It is asserted, “Sardar, who travelled near and far to find what manual labour he could, was forced to stop working altogether after being diagnosed with tuberculosis in June. That left his wife, Saraswati, putting aside most of the little food they could afford for their children.” We

⁴⁷ This report is of Dawn Hammon, [https://inhabitat.com/current-status-of-worlds-2030-sustainable-development-goals/dated: 21st September 2022](https://inhabitat.com/current-status-of-worlds-2030-sustainable-development-goals/dated:21st%20September2022). Accessed at 2 pm on 9th March 2023.

⁴⁸ <https://www.globalhungerindex.org/india.html> accessed on 9.03.2023 at 2 pm.

⁴⁹ [https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/news-feature/2022/12/19/India-hunger-starvation-data-malnutrition BHULA BEDA, India dated-19 December 2022](https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/news-feature/2022/12/19/India-hunger-starvation-data-malnutrition-BHULA-BEDA,India-dated-19December2022); accessed on 9.03.2023 at 2 pm.

⁵⁰ Activists say the government is systematically failing to classify such deaths as starvation.

had been eating only one meal daily, or the equivalent of one meal split across two meals, before Sanjoy's death," Saraswati Sardar told *The New Humanitarian* in the village of Bhula Beda, in Jhargram district."

The government has not logged a single death from starvation since 2016, but Mrinalini Paul, who works with the Right to Food and Work Network (RTFWN), a local NGO, said it's clear Sardar's death should have been recorded as one, as should many others.

The Sardar family was eligible for 35 kilos of rice and grain monthly from a government-run aid programme but had been approved for just two kilos because they lacked the right ID documents, according to Paul. "They had been without even these minimal benefits for six months," she told *The New Humanitarian*.

The district magistrate of Jhargram, refuted the allegations, telling *The Hindu* newspaper they were "baseless", while insisting that Sardar's death "was due to illness, TB, and other reasons".⁵¹

Besides, the recently published Medical Certification Cause of Death (MCCD), 2020 report found that fewer than a quarter of the 81,15,882 registered deaths in India that year had known causes. Hunger activists are alarmed that a country with 1.4 billion people can only verify the causes of 22.5% of its documented fatalities.⁵²

⁵¹ According to the World Health Organization, under-nutrition is a key driver of TB, while malnutrition also makes TB therapy less effective and raises the risk of TB-related death.

⁵² Swati Narayan, assistant professor at the School for Public Health and Human Development at O.P. Jindal Global University, told: *The New Humanitarian* that medical workers are unlikely to catch if the cause of death is starvation given how post-mortems are typically carried out...it was crucial to also consider the person's socioeconomic position and the condition of their body, including the weight of their organs, visceral fat, and diseases brought on by a weaker immune system and malnutrition...The post-mortem reports are not an accurate reflection of hunger or starvation deaths in the country... Oral autopsies are much better at determining if the cause of death was hunger."

The hunger problems pre-date COVID. India's last National Family Health Survey, which used data from 2019, found that stunting – a sign of chronic malnutrition – had risen in 11 out of the 17 states. In 13 states, wasting had also increased. Over the last two decades, the Indian government has developed the Public Distribution System (PDS) – which relies on the world's largest biometric system, Aadhaar – to try to alleviate hunger by distributing staple foods at low cost to those in most need. But experts say there are some major holes in the system. "The main limitation of the PDS is that it does little more than to provide a modicum of food and economic security to poor households". "That is certainly an important achievement, but it falls far short of ensuring adequate nutrition," ... "That requires a broader range of interventions, including child nutrition programmes, maternal care, public health measures, and quality education."

There will be even greater concern going into 2023 as the government's additional "free food programme", which has provided families with five kilos of grain every month since April 2020 as a COVID relief measure, is due to wrap up at the end of December.⁵³

⁵³ In January 2022, the central government told the Supreme Court that no states had reported any deaths due to hunger in the previous year. At issue before the three-judge bench was a public interest litigation petitioning the central government, individual states, and union territories to establish a plan for coordinating the operation of community kitchens in the fight against hunger and malnutrition.

Anun Dhawan, Ishann Dhawan, and Kunjana Singh filed the petition seeking an order to establish a national food grid for those who don't qualify for food aid under the PDS. It remains to be seen whether it will be implemented.

<https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/news-feature/2022/12/19/India-hunger-starvation-data-malnutrition>

BHULA BEDA, India dated-19 December 2022; accessed on 9.03.2023 at 2 pm. Edited by Abby Seiff.

Women's Suffering

As regards gender, about women, the National Criminal Records Bureau (NCRB) reports that India witnesses about 86 rapes every day, 46 offences against women every hour as per 2021 statistics.⁵⁴ Among states, Rajasthan (6,337) was on top of the list followed by Madhya Pradesh (2,947), Maharashtra (2,496) and Uttar Pradesh (2,845), while Delhi recorded 1,250 rape cases in 2021.⁵⁵ Overall 4,28,278 cases of 'crimes against women' were lodged across the country in 2021, with a rate of crime (per one lakh population) 64.5. The charge-sheeting rate in such offences was 77.1, the official data showed. The number of cases of crimes against women in 2020 stood at 3,71,503 and in 2019 at 4,05,326. The crimes against women category included offences like rape, rape with murder, dowry, acid attacks, suicide abetment, kidnapping, forced marriage, human trafficking, online harassment, among others.

Accessing Justice

Question on justice system are dominated by a large number of undertrial prisoners in India. Also: Why Are 66% From Marginalised groups? It is seen that the number of undertrial prisoners from marginalised castes over the last 5 years showed a 48% jump.⁵⁶ Undertrials are languishing in prison despite release

⁵⁴ [<https://www.financialexpress.com/india-news/ncrb-data-india-witnessed-86-rapes-every-day-46-offences-against-women-every-hour-in-2021/2650292/>]

⁵⁵ Written by PTI; Updated: August 31, 2022 12:22:16 pm

⁵⁶ <https://www.thequint.com/news/law/indias-undertrial-prisoners-why-are-are-66-percent-from-marginalised-castes> ROHINI ROY, Published: 24 Dec 2022, 1:42 PM IST... [Over 3 out of 5 undertrial prisoners lodged across Indian prisons, are from Dalit, Adivasi and OBC communities, according to the latest Prison Statistics of India Report (2021).

The report, released in August this year, came up during the 2022 winter session of the Parliament when Minister of State in the Ministry of Home Affairs, Ajay Kumar Mishra, said on 13 December that out of 5,54,034 prisoners, 4,27,165 of them, that is 76%, were undertrial prisoners.

order; SC wants a better system to keep tab.⁵⁷

The top court wants all states to incorporate digital record-keeping of jail data so that status of bail, discharge, etc. can be tracked.

While flagging the issue of under trial prisoners who, despite securing bail, continue to be in custody due to their inability to fulfill the conditions of bail, the Supreme Court has called upon all state governments to issue directions to jail authorities to submit details of such cases.

- (a) The name of the under trial
- (b) The offence charged
- (c) The date when the bail was granted, and
- (d) The conditions of bail that have not been met

Lastly, the chart should also indicate the duration lapsed from the date of the bail order till now.

The state will have to ensure that these details are furnished by the jail authorities to them and the data is forwarded to the National Legal Services Authority (NALSA). After that, NALSA will begin the process of making necessary suggestions on how to deal with this issue and, of course, provide legal assistance wherever

A deeper analysis of the numbers by The Quint, reveals that people from India's marginalised castes made up the majority (66%) of those imprisoned and under trial.

It is essential to note here, that undertrial prisoners are those who haven't been convicted of a crime yet, but have only been accused i.e. the charges mentioned against them haven't been proven. They are still, literally, 'under trial'.

Undertrial prisoners, thus, are those that have been imprisoned during the investigation, inquiry, or trial of the crime for which they were arrested.

⁵⁷ <https://www.indiatoday.in/law/story/undertrials-languishing-prison-despite-release-order-sc-wants-better-system-keep-tab-2306328-2022-12-07>
Report by Vidya

necessary. The bench said that NALSA could also seek assistance from Tata Institute of Social Sciences (TISS) as it is stated that such an endeavour has been made by them already in Maharashtra. The bench said that assistance would have to be provided seeking variation of the terms of the bail in such cases.

Pendency of cases in courts is a matter of challenge to justice system. “Pending cases across various courts in the country are moving towards the five crore-mark with an over 4.32 crore backlog in subordinate courts, according to data shared by the government in Rajya Sabha on Thursday. In separate written replies, Law Minister said as on December 31, 2022, the total pending cases in district and subordinate courts was pegged at over 4.32 crore. He also said over 69,000 cases are pending in the Supreme Court, while there is a backlog of more than 59 lakh cases in the country’s 25 high courts.

As per details available on the Supreme Court website, 69,511 cases were pending in the top court as on February 1.” There are 59,87,477 cases pending in high courts across the country, as per the information available on National Judicial Data Grid (NJDG) on February 1, 2023.” Out of these, 10.30 *lakh* cases were pending in the Allahabad High Court — the biggest high court of the country. The Sikkim High Court has the least number of 171 cases. The total pending cases come to 4,92,67,373 or over 4.92 crore.⁵⁸

Troubling pendency

The key reason for the mounting of pending cases can be attributed to shifting the role of the Supreme Court from adjudicating cases of constitutional significance into a regular court of appeals. According to legal experts, most of the cases that the Supreme Court was handling daily are either appeals from various high

⁵⁸ India NewsPress Trust of India Updated: February 09, 2023 8:58 pm IST

courts or cases of gross violation of individual's fundamental rights. But this role was never meant for the apex court.

From 1950 to 1921, the number of Supreme Court judges has increased nearly four times. Even then, case pendency has steadily kept rising. Around 5,580 or 25% of posts are lying empty in the subordinate courts, which leads to poor Judges to Population Ratio, as India has only 20 judges per million population. Earlier, Law Commission had recommended 50 judges per million.

The laid down procedure of allowing a maximum of three adjournments per case is not followed in over 50 per cent of the matters being heard by courts, leading to rising pendency of cases. Low budgetary allocation is leading to poor infrastructure; Burden of government cases is too much. Police are quite often handicapped in undertaking effective investigation for want of modern and scientific tools to collect evidences.

A weak judiciary has a negative effect on social development, which leads to: lower per capita income; higher poverty rates; poorer public infrastructure; and, higher crime rates. Overcrowding of the prisons, already infrastructure deficient, in some cases beyond 150% of the capacity, results in "violation of human rights".

Timeline set out for computerisation of all the courts, as a necessary step towards setting up of e- courts be followed. All India Judicial Service, which would benefit the subordinate judiciary by increasing quality of judges and help reduce the pendency. Electronic filing of cases: e-Courts are a welcome step in this direction, as they give case status and case history of all the pending cases across High courts and Subordinate courts bringing ease of access to information. Alternate dispute resolution (ADR): As stated in the Conference on National Initiative to Reduce Pendency and Delay in Judicial System- Legal Services Authorities should

undertake pre-litigation mediation so that the inflow of cases into courts can be regulated. The Lok Adalat should be organized regularly for settling civil and family matters. Gram Nyayalayas, as an effective way to manage small claim disputes from rural areas which will help in decreasing the workload of the judicial institution. Village Legal Care and Support Centres can also be established by the High Courts to work at grass root level to make the State litigation friendly.

The fundamental requirement of a good judicial administration is accessibility, affordability and speedy justice, which will not be realized until and unless the justice delivery system is made within the reach of the individual in a time bound manner and within a reasonable cost.

Children Drop-outing from Schools

Effectiveness of education system is a key to attainment of many goals. Unfortunately, a recent survey by National Statistical Office (NSO) has revealed that around 12.6% of students drop out of school in India, 19.8% discontinued education at the secondary level, while 17.5% dropped out at the upper primary level. As per the survey, a dropout is an “ever-enrolled person” who does not complete the last level of education for which he/she has enrolled and is currently not attending any educational institution. The Government’s Right to Education Act and National Policy on Education may have been motivating to provide education to all but it is equally important to analyze the sustainability and efficiency of the education system. Dropout rates are considered to be a great wastage in the education system, not only do many students leave school without acquiring basic skills, but their premature departure represents a significant waste of scarce education resources.⁵⁹

⁵⁹ Prakarti Walia, School dropouts in India: the causes and prevention, <https://www.turnthebus.org/blog/school-dropouts-in-india-the-cause-and> accessed on 10th March 2023 at 3 pm

UNICEF's U-Report poll 2022 reveals that 38% of respondents knew at least one female student to have dropped out of school. The UDISE+ 2020-21 report shows that the dropout rate for secondary level education was 14.6%.⁶⁰

The Unified District Information System for Education Plus (UDISE+) report said that the dropout rate among primary students went up from 0.8 per cent in 2020-21 to 1.45 per cent in 2021-22. The report said that more than 8 lakh new girl students enrolled in the year 2021-22, while the number of students enrolled under SC, ST, OBC and Children with Special Needs (CWSN) increased.

The rate for drop out for upper primary students spiked from 1.9 to 3.02 per cent, said the report, which provides a comprehensive study that provides information about enrollment and dropout rates of school students, the number of teachers and infrastructural facilities like toilets, buildings, electricity, hand wash facilities etc. But at the same time, enrolment of students across all the sections from primary to higher secondary went up by 0.95 crores in the same period to stand at 26.52 crores, out of which 13.28 crore were boys and 12.28 crore girls.⁶¹

Social Peace and Progress

Absence of social peace is a big issue obstructing the way forward to equality, justice and peace. A thirty years' latest history of unfortunate incidents of communal violence, preceded by so much of it, show the gravity of it.⁶² In 1989, violence between Hindus and the Muslims in the Bhagalpur resulted in death of around one thousand people (mostly Muslims) and displacement of around

⁶⁰ <https://www.telegraphindia.com/edugraph/news/unicef-india-report-highlights-alarming-rise-in-dropout-rates-of-female-school-students/cid/1858585>

⁶¹ <https://www.newindianexpress.com/nation/2022/nov/04/school-dropout-new-enrolment-both-on-rise-finds-new-study-2514800.html>

⁶² <https://www.gktoday.in/topic/communal-riots-in-india-key-incidents-and-trends/>

50,000 people. This riot had started at a time when Ram Janmabhoomi Movement was on peak. The tensions escalated at a time when Muharram and Bisheri Puja festivities coincided. Babri Mosque demolition, 1992 resulted in communal riots for several months which resulted in the death of at least 2000 people. The Godhra riots were caused by fire in coaches of Sabarmati Express which killed 58 Hindu “*kar sevaks*” who were returning from Ayodhya. This was followed by communal riots between Hindus and Muslims in Gujarat for several months resulting into killing of thousands. The official estimates states that atleast 790 Muslims and 254 Hindus were killed during the riots. Such incidents should be stopped.

In 2012, there were communal riots in Kokrajhar between indigenous Bodos (Tribal, Christian & Hindu faith) and the Muslims after unidentified persons killed four youths of Bodo tribes. The riots resulted in the death of around 80 people and destruction of 500 villages. In 2013, communal clashes broke out between the *Jats* and Muslim community in Muzaffarnagar district of Uttar Pradesh. The riots resulted in the death of 62 people and displaced more than 5000 people. The riots were labelled as the worst violence in the recent history of Uttar Pradesh.

In 2020 Delhi riots took place which were multiple waves of bloodshed, property destruction, and rioting in North East Delhi, beginning on 23 February 2020 and caused chiefly by Hindu mobs attacking Muslims. Of the 53 people killed, two-thirds were Muslims who were shot, slashed with repeated blows, or set on fire. The dead also included a policeman, an intelligence officer and over a dozen Hindus, who were shot or assaulted. More than a week after the violence had ended, hundreds of wounded were languishing in inadequately staffed medical facilities and corpses were being found in open drains. By mid-March many Muslims had remained missing.⁶³

⁶³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2020_Delhi_riots

Communal riots in India are more politically motivated than caused by the religious factors. The Madan Commission, which was constituted to look into the causes of communal riots in Maharashtra in 1970s, had emphasized that the primary builders of communal tensions are politicians and communalists. Apart from political interests, economic interests also play an important role in instigating communal clashes in India. For example, illicit trade practices can result in communal violence. In most of the riots, the majority of victims did have nothing to do with communal hatred. In other words, in majority of cases, the perpetrators of violence and victims of violence are different persons.

According to statistics, occurrence of communal riots is more in North India than in the South India. The possibility of recurrence of communal riots in places already affected by such riots is greater than those areas which has not witnessed communal riots at all.

The possibility of communal riots is higher in urban areas when compared with that of the rural areas. This is due to the presence of large number of minority population in urban areas.

Most of the riots have occurred during clash of religious festivals. In India, communal riots are also commonly preceding elections. In few instances, communal riots have been used by the state governments to divert the attention of people from genuine problems. Further, earlier, the communal violence used to be sudden and sporadic. But in recent times, the communal riots are well planned and executed to suit the interests of the political class.⁶⁴

Mob lynching incidents, without an expected recourse to law, have increased in frequency and gravity in the recent years, raising a

⁶⁴ <https://www.gktoday.in/topic/communal-riots-in-india-key-incidents-and-trends/>

question mark on India's indexing on the standards of equality, peace, justice, poverty and education. This needs immediate action for taking the rout of fair attainment of sustainable development goals of reduced inequalities, peace, justice, partnership and literacy.

Social Democracy

A 'social democracy' is a specific type of welfare state and policy regime described as being universalist, supportive of collective bargaining, and more supportive of public provision of welfare. Social democracy, as on the ground, is a government system that has similar commitment to values of socialism, but works within a capitalist framework. The thought, as emerging from democracy, where people have a say in government actions, supports a competitive economy with money while also helping people in securing jobs.

India's endeavours for social democracy have to address the issue of participation in state activities of all, though, a largely diverse group of Indian people, with social, economic, language, racial, religious, aspirational, gender and caste diversities. Adherence to basic constitutional values can be the best course. Any deviance from the balanced and universally accepted norms will be disastrous. Since 1950, the endeavour in this direction shows that the constitutionally positive approach has helped the best the improvements in human index of the country. Deviance from that approach has always culminated in injury, rather bloodshed. Equality and social adhesiveness is the best satisfying for the core concepts of all faiths, philosophies and cultures worth the name. India's traditional wisdom need to be invoked as that is truly in consonance with any universally values constituting the social democracy, best for peace, harmony and dignity, without any tinge of imposition. That is where India can act as the Vishwaguru in the attainment of sustainable development goals.

V-Conclusion

The United Nations came into existence “to save succeeding generations from the scourge of war, which twice in our life-time has brought untold sorrow to mankind, and to reaffirm faith in fundamental human rights, in the dignity and worth of the human person, in the equal rights of men and women and of nations large and small, and to establish conditions under which justice and respect for the obligations arising from treaties and other sources of international law can be maintained, and to promote social progress and better standards of life in larger freedom”. A subsequent declarations and programmes assured “everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status. Furthermore, no distinction shall be made on the basis of the political, jurisdictional or international status of the country or territory to which a person belongs. Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person. No one shall be held in slavery or servitude; slavery and the slave trade shall be prohibited in all their forms. No one shall be subjected to torture or to cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment. Everyone has the right to recognition everywhere as a person before the law. All are equal before the law and are entitled without any discrimination to equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration and against any incitement to such discrimination. Everyone has the right to an effective remedy by the competent national tribunals for acts violating the fundamental rights granted him by the constitution or by law. No one shall be subjected to arbitrary arrest, detention or exile. Everyone is entitled in full equality to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of his rights and obligations and of any criminal charge against him.

On the turn of the century in 2000, the United Nations adopted Millennium Development Goals. Setting another target for 2030, Sustainable Development Goals have been adopted as an ambitious

programme for 2015-2030 with expected achievements of no poverty; zero hunger; good health and well being; quality education; gender equality; clean water and sanitation; affordable and clean energy; decent work and economic growth; industry, innovation and infrastructure; reduced inequality; sustainable cities and communities; responsible consumption and production; climate action; life below water; life on land; peace and justice strong institutions; and partnerships to achieve the goals. After, **on 25th September 2015**, the General Assembly of the United Nations adopted the '2030- Agenda' for Sustainable Development that includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals, half of the time is already over. Pandemic of Corona came as a very adverse intruder from 2019 to 2022. During the left over period of seven and a half years, the global partnerships to achieve the goals should be exemplarily vibrant, sincere and targeted. All the universities, research institutes must take up programmes for research and training to achieve the goals. Nation States must prioritise the SDGs as per their ground situations and cooperate with all other countries for sharing expertise and resources. Social conflicts should be eliminated by creating multi-cultural understanding and prevent state agencies from becoming a part of these conflicts. Media in each county should support the popularization of SDGs as prime human needs demanding attention of all human beings together. Voluntary sector must play a positive role in advancing and reviewing the achievements with a reasonable frequency to give feedback to the concerned agencies. Market regulations and policies should be reviewed in the context of SDGs. Justice systems should be geared up to new needs making them accessible to the person at the lowest rung of the society. Quality education should be recognized as the fundamental right in its true sense and implantation programmes must be appropriate, comprehensive and effective. Respect for all human beings with equality and dignity should not be compromised by any means. Firm feeling of sense of security should be created in all human being, irrespective of differences in caste, creed, colour, gender, region, language or any other, respecting their right to life, equality and dignity. Those persons or nations who are working against this agenda should be motivated to show respect for humanity with diversity.

INDIAN APPROACH TO INTERNATIONAL ARBITRATION –THE NEED TO FIND PEACE IN THE UNDECLARED WAR BETWEEN LEGISLATURE AND JUDICIARY

Saikat Mukherjee*

Abstract

The Arbitration and Conciliation Act of 1996 was enacted keeping in mind the contemporary developments in the field of arbitration in the world in general and in India in specific. The policy that went behind the formation of this law was one of much debate primarily because it was believed that the way it got extended to the Indian framework ensured that the rule of law principles suffered. Ever since then, a pattern has been seen whereby the judiciary tries to interpret the law in a method which is conflicting to the primary legislative intent thereby leading to a constant tussle between the legislature and the judiciary, at the expense of the law itself. The situation has only further worsened keeping in mind the insistence of the international community to adopt the “pro-arbitration” approach, something which itself is very subjective and which keeps on changing depending on the stakeholders in the game. In this background, India has so far not been able to reach the standards of being an “arbitration friendly” jurisdiction. This paper tries to bring out ways in which the judiciary and the legislature are responsible for complicating the jurisprudence surrounding arbitration in India and the ways in which the same can be mitigated so that the aim of India being an “arbitration friendly” jurisdiction can be met.

Key words – Arbitration, Rule of Law, Pro-arbitration approach, Foreign-seated arbitrations, Legislature.

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Rule of Law in International Arbitration

Rule of law typically refers to the presence of procedural and substantive principles that tend to restrict the use of arbitrary power by governmental institutions.¹ In other words it can be defined as that collection of uniformly recognized values which are a sine qua non for the effective functioning of a politico-legal system. It mainly aims at ensuring that the citizenry, for whom the system exists in the first place have faith in the justice delivery mechanism of the country. Rule of law assumes an even greater importance in the field of international arbitration given the number of players and the varying foreign substantive laws at play. For these players to have the required trust and confidence in a country's dispute resolution mechanism, it is important for the country's legal procedure to be integrated. Such integrity is to be ensured through prospective application of the laws which are otherwise general in design and promise consistency of application.² Incorporation of poorly drafted provisions leading to unnecessary amendments alongside constant ignoring of intellectual research-based recommendations have led to these expectations being compromised. Moreover, in common law countries, courts (through the exercise of their "judge made laws") are entrusted with the duty of filling the gaps wherever necessary thereby ensuring that the development of law, to its fullest potential takes place. However, while exercising this power, it is imperative upon the judiciary to limit itself to the boundaries of the statute and not engage in unrestricted legal realism. This has been a practice being followed by some courts in India who on account of trying to mold the law to be so called "arbitration friendly", have altogether dumped the interpretation which the legislature might have intended. This tendency has led to a constant back and forth

¹ Naomi Choi, *rule of law – political philosophy*, BRITANNICA (April 25, 2017, 09:06 AM), <https://www.britannica.com/topic/rule-of-law>

² Colleen Murphy, *Lon Fuller and the Moral Value of Rule of Law*, 24 LAW AND PHILOSOPHY 239, 240–241 (2005)

between the judiciary and the law makers with the overturning of awards by the courts being an altogether common phenomenon.

These expectations from both the law-making organ as well as the law interpreting organ are fundamental in so far as the choice of law of the parties governing the arbitration is concerned even though the same may come at the expense of a system being “pro-arbitration”, a term which itself is vague at worst and subjective at best. It is defined as system of international arbitration wherein the players ask themselves as to whether a practice or policy favors the practices of international arbitration or not.³ From one perspective, a practice might appear to be pro-arbitration whereas from the other it might not. For example, there has been an ever-increasing call for transparency in commercial international arbitration even though the same is opposed to the principles of confidentiality. By mandatory implementations of the “opt in” as opposed to the “opt out” confidentiality provisions, there has been constant attempts to try and forcefully make public the awards of arbitration even when the parties prefer otherwise.⁴

This paper attempts to emphasize on the need for remembering the rule of law principles while considering meeting the pro-arbitration values. Further, it will look to explore a recent example of the judiciary involving itself in creativity in the field of arbitration law and how the international community welcomed it as a pro-arbitration step. Thereafter, before concluding, it lays down the problems that are being faced due to the plethora of amendment being made to the law and the absolute necessity to have a clear thought process before amending the law any further.

³ G.A. Bermann, *What does it mean to be ‘pro-arbitration’?* 34 *ARBITRATION INTERNATIONAL* 338, 339–340 (2018).

⁴ Constantine Partasides & Simon Maynard, *Raising the curtain on English Arbitration*, 33 *ARBITRATION INTERNATIONAL* 197, 202 (2017)

The undefined position of law – arena for creativity

There stands no doubt to the claim that the Indian judiciary has played a leading role insofar as the development of jurisprudence surrounding arbitration in India is concerned. Very often, the same has been termed as even “pro arbitration”. Although such activism by the judiciary is welcomed by those who consider that this will play a role in India becoming the go to international arbitration destination, others caution that the manner in which the developments are happening would end up having long term ramifications.

Reference here can be drawn to the enforcement and recognition of emergency awards. In the recent case landmark case involving *Amazon*, wherein the constitutional courts in India allowed the enforcement of India-seated emergency arbitration awards. It is worth noting that the same are not recognized by the law of land i.e., Section 17 of the Arbitration and Conciliation Act, 1996.⁵ With this, the courts while going contrary to the legislative intent, placed wrong reliance on the jurisprudence in existence. Further it keeps open the question as to why foreign seated emergency arbitration awards not backed by law and require indirect enforcement.⁶ Such interpretation keeps rule of law in the backseat and creates an uncertain environment for arbitration in the country on account of the constantly changing position of law. This creates a situation where international clients then look to other neutral destinations for seating their arbitrations, jurisdictions which promise stability of law as opposed to India.

⁵ Amazon.com NIV Investment Holdings LLC vs Future Retail Ltd, 2021 SCC OnLine SC 557

⁶ Dipen Sabharwal KC & Aditya Singh, *Supreme Court of India paves way for enforcement of emergency arbitration awards in India-seated arbitrations*, WHITE & CASE (Aug. 16, 2021, 05:13 PM), <https://www.whitecase.com/insight-alert/supreme-court-india-paves-way-enforcement-emergency-arbitration-awards-india-seated>

The Supreme Court of India made another attempt at trying to enhance party autonomy when it was faced with two questions. The first pertained to whether a non-Indian seat of arbitration can be chosen by two domestic Indian parties and secondly whether in such an award will be considered a “foreign award” with special reference to those instances where the subject matter of the contract itself is devoid of any foreign element. The apex court of the country answered both questions in the affirmative and for doing so interpreted the term “international” in two different ways under the same law.

There exists a dichotomy between foreign seated arbitrations and India-seated arbitrations insofar as the present Arbitration Act is concerned. The latter is covered by Part 1 of the act of 1996 whereas the former is covered by Part 2. Part 2 essentially looks to effectuate the 1958 New York Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards as well as the 1927 Geneva Convention on the Execution of Foreign Arbitral Awards. By the application of Section 2(2) of the 1996 Act, only certain parts of Part 1 are applicable on foreign seated arbitrations whereas for the majority parts, they remain mutually exclusive.

The term “international commercial arbitration” has been construed so under Section 2(1)(f) that a mere choice of a foreign seat would not automatically make an arbitration international. This position has remained both pre and post the 2015 amendment. Moreover, since the coming into force of the act of 1996, it can safely be said that India has embraced the definition of foreign award as provided under the New York Convention. Although this convention primarily deals with international commercial arbitration in the first place, it does not define the term per se. It only says that a foreign award will be that award which is obtained beyond enforcing countries territory. Article 1 of the said convention, read with Article 3⁷ provides for the enforcement and

⁷ Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Arbitral Awards art. I(1), June 10, 1958, 330 U.N.T.S 38.

recognition of foreign awards. The convention remains cautiously silent on what would the phrase “*arbitral awards not considered as domestic awards*” or “arbitral awards made in the territory of another state” mean thereby allowing the contracting state to decide for themselves.

In the landmark case of *PASL Wind Solutions*⁸, the apex court of the country had provided its opinion on whether two Indian parties are entitled to have a foreign seat of arbitration and whether the award can be considered to be an international award. The appellant in the present matter had not at the outset objected to the order of the court which allowed two Indian companies to have an arbitration seated outside India in Zurich. However, when posed with an unfavorable order, they subsequently decided to raise the issue as late as at the stage of enforcement. At that point in time, this proposition was an unsettled position of law in India.

At this point, it must be remembered that the New York Convention applies to those international arbitration agreements which provide for foreign awards with a foreign element or flavors involving international commerce and trade⁹. Section 44 of the act of 1996 provides the basic elements that need to be present for an award to be referred to as a foreign award. The said section, on account of having the phrase “*unless the context otherwise requires*” clearly states that the rule mentioned herein under is the rule to be applied in normal circumstances unless the context requires something different. The argument before the court was that for the application of Section 44, the award under consideration must have been that of an international commercial arbitration. The court was faced with the question as to whether the term “*international commercial arbitration*” as defined under Section 2(1)(f) was to be extended to

⁸ PASL Wind Solutions Pvt Ltd vs GE Power Conversion (India) Pvt Ltd, 2021 SCC Online SC 331

⁹ Gas Authority of India Ltd vs Spie Capag, 1993 SCC OnLine Del 561

the present situation or not. In its decision, it categorically stated that on account of Section 44 not being party central but rather seat centric as opposed to Section 2(1)(f) which is party centric, the definition provided in the latter cannot be extended to the former. Hence, with regards to Section 44, residence, nationality, or domicile becomes irrelevant.

Further, the court also laid emphasis on Section 2(2) of the act as per which certain provisions of Part 1 would be applicable when there is a foreign place of arbitration involved in an international commercial arbitration. The court categorically held that both parts of the act are mutually exclusive of each other, and that Section 2(2) does not allow bridging of the two parts.¹⁰ It reasoned that the clause is a seat-centric one and not a party.¹¹ Further, it also opined that those provisions of Part 1 of the Act which typically apply to international commercial arbitrations which are foreign seated including provisions for court ordered interim reliefs will be applicable only between Indian parties.¹² In a nutshell, the court has essentially provided two different definitions for Part 1 and Part 2 as well as for Sections 2(2) and 2(1)(f) of Part 1.

Although, these varying definitions are considered pro-arbitration on account of them being in favor of party autonomy, the question is at what cost? Typically, when a statute provides a definition section, the intent of the legislature is that the words as defined be construed only in that manner for the entire statute or at least that particular chapter even though the definitions might be contrary to what they mean in the common parlance. For example, Section 44 of the act uses the phrase “*in this chapter*” which indicates the fact that “*international commercial arbitration*” as construed in Section 2(1)(f) might not be the same as in Chapter 1 of Part 2.¹³ Even if one

¹⁰ PASL, supra note 10, at 38 & 50.

¹¹ Id. at 38.

¹² Id. at 38 & 100.

¹³ Id. at 60.

is to consider otherwise, it is a settled proposition of law that the text of the statute, on account of it containing inter-related parts must be construed as a whole. Further, it is also a settled position that a word must have only one meaning in the entire statute wherever compatible unless a different meaning is expressly provided.¹⁴ A decision of the Rajasthan High Court of the year 2020 is worth noting in this regard. It held that typically a definition clause is not just restricted to any particular chapter but rather extends to the whole of the act. If it is construed otherwise, then the results would be absurd and abnormal.¹⁵ This holding was contrary to the one of the Supreme Court in the PASL case wherein even within the same part, two different definitions were accorded.

The ruling of the Rajasthan High Court was not without relevant judicial precedents.

In the case of *Atlas Exports Industries Ltd vs Kotak and Co*¹⁶, a foreign award between two Indian parties in arbitration was enforced under the Foreign Awards (Recognition and Enforcement) Act, 1961. The decision was pertaining to Sections 23 and 28 of the Indian Contract Act with regards to the fact that not providing the ordinary remedy available under Indian Law would be contrary to what the general principles of public policy would provide. It further held that since the parties had chosen to not raise the contention at hand prior to or during the arbitration or before the High Court hence they were estopped from raising the same before the Supreme Court for the first time. Moreover, this particular matter had a foreign element involved because the goods in question were supplied by a Hong Kong based company through and Indian company from Hong Kong itself.

¹⁴ ANTONIN SCALIA & BRYAN GARNER, *READING LAW – THE INTERPRETATION OF LEGAL TEXTS* 274–282 (2012).

¹⁵ *Barmenco Indian Underground Mining Services LLP vs Hindustan Zinc Ltd.*, 2020 SCC OnLine Raj 1190.

¹⁶ *Atlas Exports Industries Ltd vs Kotak and Co.* (1997) 7 SCC 61.

In another landmark case of *Sasan Power*¹⁷, the High Court of Madhya Pradesh expressed its approval of two Indian companies arbitrating outside India. This was a case wherein all rights, obligations and liabilities of an American company were assigned via an assignment agreement to the Indian subsidiary of the American Company in an agreement between the American Company and an Indian Company. It was argued on behalf of the Indian Company that since post assignment the essence of the contract now rested between two Indian companies hence Part 2 of the Act of 1996 would not be applicable at all. However, the court held that a foreign element was indeed involved because the dispute necessitated the perusal of the rights as well as the obligations of the American company under the initial agreement as well as the assignment agreement.

In the matter of *GMR Energy Ltd vs Doosan Power Systems India*¹⁸, the Delhi High Court opined that Indian parties are normally free to choose a non-Indian seat of arbitration. However, in doing so it incorrectly relied on the *Sasan Power Ltd* case which exclusively dealt with the involvement of a foreign element in arbitration¹⁹. Moreover, in the matter before the Delhi High Court as well, there was the presence of a foreign element because the defendant per se was the wholly owned subsidiary of its Korean counterpart which had entered into a MOU with the plaintiff and had subsequently negotiated a payment schedule of the outstanding debt. Hence, one can conclude that the two Indian parties choosing a foreign seat was based on the involvement of a foreign element.

¹⁷ *Sasan Power Ltd vs North American Coal Corporation.*, 2015 SCC OnLine MP 7417

¹⁸ *GMR Energy Ltd vs Doosan Power Systems India.*, 2017 SCC OnLine Del 11625.

¹⁹ Shalaka Patil & Jeet Shroff, *Delhi High Court's Decision in GMR vs Doosan: Two steps forward, two steps back?*, KLUWER ARBITRATION BLOG (Jan. 01, 2018, 12:21 PM), Delhi High Court's decision in GMR v. Doosan: Two steps forward, two steps back? - Kluwer Arbitration Blog

Through this journey, one realizes that the PASL case was one of the first where without the involvement of a foreign element, a foreign seat of arbitration was chosen by two completely Indian parties. Relying on the GMR Energy judgement and that of Sasan Power, the apex court of the country ended up overruling the Bombay High Court decision in the case of *Addhar Mercantile Private Ltd vs Shree Jagadamba Agrico Exports Private Ltd*²⁰ as well as the case of *Seven Islands Shipping Ltd vs Sab Petroleums Ltd*²¹. In both these decisions, the Bombay High Court had relied heavily upon the judgement in the case of *TDM Infrastructure Private Ltd vs UE Development India Private Ltd*²² and essentially did not allow two India parties to be subjected to a foreign law of arbitration.

In the case of Addhar Mercantile, two Indian parties had entered into an arbitration agreement whereby the seat for arbitration was kept as either Singapore or India with the rider that English law would apply in case of the former. The Bombay High Court, in line with the judgement of TDM Infrastructure held that Indian parties should be subjected to the Indian law and that any deviation from the same would be opposed to public policy. It further held that the arbitration is to be conducted as per Section 28(1)(a) of the act in India itself. What must be understood is that the matter per se did not talk about the law governing the arbitration but rather the choice of the substantive law. The court in the matter of PASL was succinctly silent on the question of two Indian parties wanting to choose a non-Indian substantive law. However, the overturning of the Addhar judgement might be seen as the parties being given the option of choosing the foreign substantive law in a non-international foreign arbitration.

²⁰ Addhar Mercantile Private Ltd. vs Shree Jagadamba Agrico Exports Private Ltd., 2015 SCC OnLine Bom 7752

²¹ Seven Islands Shipping Ltd vs Sah Petroleums Ltd., (2012) 5 Mah LJ 822.

²² TDM Infrastructure Private Ltd. vs UE Development India Private Ltd., (2008) 14 SCC 271

The court in the case of PASL also looked to answer the question as to whether the choosing of a foreign seat for arbitration by two Indian parties would be opposed to public policy or not under Section 23 of the Indian Contract Act. It firstly opined that the term “*public policy*” as mentioned under Section 23 is a relative concept which is subject to modifications depending upon the advancement in science and technology. The parties freedom to contract must be balanced viz-a-viz there being an undeniable harm to the general public. In terms of the provisions of Section 28, the court held that the provision does not make any reference to the nationality of the parties as such. Further, in the absence of Section 28(1)(a) of the act of 1996 making any reference to the conducting of arbitration between two Indian parties in a foreign seat, such an interpretation should not be automatically provided.

While looking to provide justification, the court laid emphasis on the principles of international comity, Section 48 of the Arbitration Act of 1996 as well as the balance of convenience between freedom to contract and the harm caused to the public. It further held that since there is per se no contravention of public policy of India or provisions of Indian law, party autonomy should prevail. However, one must keep in mind that parties do not have a right to waive off the right to challenge an award under Section 34 by mutual consent.

As can be very pertinently seen from above, this approach of the judiciary can be concluded as pro arbitration and pro-party autonomy to a large extent although the same comes at the cost of deviating from the primary legislative intent. It also creates a large pool of questions which then come up for litigation. Moreover, since the act keeps getting amended and judicial pronouncements keep getting overturned by subsequent matters, the position of law remains unsettled. In this background, it is imperative for the judiciary and the legislature to work side by side in order to create a more suitable environment for arbitration.

Well thought out provisions –the need of the hour.

The approach of the Indian legislature in the field of arbitration has created an air of instability surrounding the entire mechanism in India. This has resulted in India not being seen as a preferred destination for arbitration by foreign parties. Moreover, the ongoing tussle between the judiciary and the legislature has added fuel to fire. Reference here can be drawn to the Amendment Act of 2015²³. This particular amendment did away with the erstwhile automatic stay on enforcement of arbitral awards. It also made certain important changes to the factors present erstwhile for setting aside arbitral awards. However, it failed to clarify as to whether these changes as to whether it would be applicable prospectively or retrospectively. The judicial proceedings subsequently clarified that it should be made prospectively applicable to all such court proceedings which have commenced post the amendment coming into force and that the same would be without regard to the time when the arbitration had commenced. This position however got reversed by the amendment of 2019 which looked to deal with those court proceedings which had begun after the amendment but were based on arbitrations initiated prior to the amendment. The difference of opinion between the legislature and the judiciary was seen to continue as Section 87 of the act of 1996, inserted via the Amendment of 2019 was struck down by the Supreme Court²⁴ on account of it being unconstitutional.

Reference can also be made to the Ordinance of 2020 which acted as the precursor to the Amendment Act of 2021, which so far fortunately has not resulted in a tussle. Via this amendment, Section 36 of the Act of 1996 got amended. It now made it compulsory for

²³ Suraj Prakash, Aditya Chauhan and Keshav Tibarewalla, *Recourse against Arbitral Awards in India: Navigating Murky Waters*, 51 INT’L COM. ARB. REV., 52, 60–66 (2021)

²⁴ Hindustan Construction Company Ltd vs Union of India., 2019 SCC OnLine SC 1520.

the courts to stay the award unconditionally if it found prima facie that the contract between the parties, the arbitration agreement, or the award itself was induced by corruption/fraud. Such an amendment which was anyway forcefully introduced first via an ordinance came as a surprise to all interested parties primarily because it wasn't believed that any change to the arbitration law in India was needed²⁵. Some even called the amendment suspicious since it was introduced in a hasty manner just prior to the hearing for enforcement in the case of *Antrix Corporation Ltd vs Devas Multimedia Private Ltd*²⁶, a case wherein an award had been passed against the Indian government by the Permanent Court of Arbitration at Hague. Given the retrospective effect of the amendment, the suspicion appears to be well founded. Such an approach from the Indian law makers by putting the rule of law on the backseat has essentially pulled India back by a few decades in its dream of becoming a global arbitration-friendly seat.

Moreover, it appears that the legislation has been drafted rather hastily since it is next to impossible to have prima facie understanding of whether corruption/fraud has taken place or not without listening to detailed arguments²⁷. Without there being a mandatory requirement of security or any other pre-condition, parties would then look to abuse the procedure of law in order to derail enforcement. Further, through this amendment, the legislature has created an altogether separate class of cases i.e., those involving corruption or fraud by attaching a proviso the Section 36. This in itself creates new issues of interpretation because typically under Section 36, the court had the option of

²⁵ Payaswini Upadhyay, *A Change to the Arbitration Law Whose Purpose Is Unclear*, BQ PRIME (Nov 24, 2020, 12:48 PM), *A Change To The Arbitration Law Whose Purpose Is Unclear* (bqprime.com)

²⁶ Gary Born, Steven P, S Irani, *Recent Amendments to Arbitral Laws: India and Singapore*, WILMERHALE (Dec. 15, 2020, 05:23 PM), *Recent Amendments to Arbitral Laws: India and Singapore* | WilmerHale

²⁷ Id.

attaching conditions before ordering stay of enforcement. The mandate on staying of the award in case of corruption or fraud has essentially done away with the power of the judiciary to attach any conditions before ordering a grant of stay²⁸.

At this juncture, one can also refer to Section 42A of the Arbitration Act which was added via the 2019 Amendment itself. This section puts a positive obligation of confidentiality on parties, institutions, and arbitrators to the only exception of disclosing the information if the same is required for enforcement of the award. It appears so that the exception to confidentiality can be extended to the cases involving “public interest” as well despite the fact that Section 42A contains a non-obstante clause. Reference here can be drawn to the case of *R.S. Sravan Kumar vs Central Public Information Officer*²⁹ wherein the Central Information Commission had allowed an application under the Right to Information Act to know the fees charged by the legal team arguing for Antrix Corporation Ltd in an international arbitration. The said entity is the commercial wing of Indian Space Research Organization (ISRO). Such divulgence of information on the ground that the authority is a public entity is directly against the wordings of Section 42A.

Party autonomy in an arbitration proceeding is paramount. Hence, there needs to be a fine balance between the principles of confidentiality and transparency. Blind adherence to transparency would directly come in the way of promoting party autonomy. The Report of the Srikrishna Committee³⁰ which had advocated for the introduction of the provision in the first place provided no guidelines to understand the limits on confidentiality. The report

²⁸ R.S. Sravan Kumar vs Central Public Information Officer, 2019 SCC OnLine CIC 9981

²⁹ Justice B.N. Srikrishna, *Report of the High Level Committee to Review the Institutionalisation of Arbitration Mechanism in India*, MINISTRY OF LAW AND JUSTICE (July, 30, 2017) MergedFile (legalaffairs.gov.in)

does lay emphasis on the duty of confidentiality as seen in UK and Singapore as well as draws inference from the Ordinance on Hong Kong Arbitration, yet the provision does not incorporate within its ambit, the exceptions allowed in the common law countries. Further, it does not allow the courts the room to formulate such exceptions. As a result, this provision has been at the receiving end of much criticism not only for the aforementioned reasons but also for not having an opt out option or not being applicable to witnesses.

Given the presence of numerous such provisions which stink of ambiguity, the legislature has had to amend the law multiple times. Moreover, the ambiguity in the law mandates parties to undergo lengthy litigation which defeats the very purpose of ADR mechanism in the first place. Hence, there is a need for the legislature to have proper discussions and be appreciative of recommendations before introducing amendments to the law.

Conclusion

There stands no doubt that the interpretation given by the court to ambiguous provisions of the law governing arbitration in India is often appreciated by the arbitration community as being “pro-arbitration”. Although the same might be appreciated by various stakeholders of the game on account of them being inclusive enough, the same has come at the expense of legitimacy, certainty, predictability and most importantly stability. By going against the legislative intent, the upholders of rule of law have essentially shaken the very foundation of the principle. On the other hand, equal blame is to be taken by the legislature as well because it has brought about multiple amendments to the law on arbitration in India without understanding the need for discussion. This is the primary reason why the judiciary has had to interfere time and again in the interpretation of the law.

When it comes to making India the hub for international arbitration,

emphasis lays on the shoulders of both the judiciary and the legislature. The policy surrounding arbitration in India should be to further the legitimacy of the mechanism of alternative dispute resolution and should be based on the countries own legal system and values. The status requires emphasis on rule of law and not rule of the so-called pro-arbitration lobby because the only way India would progress in its aims of becoming the hotbed of international arbitration is by being a jurisdiction which promises stability of law backed by the principles of rule of law.

**INDIA'S TARGET TO BE A CARBO-FREE COUNTRY:
“LIFE”
(Lifestyle for the environment)**

Veenu Gupta*
Nidhi Gupta**

For us, the most important component is the incorporation of a sustainable lifestyle. The world today went in that direction by putting it in the implementation plan to combat climate change. It is PM Narendra Singh Modi who has made the pitch for an environment-friendly lifestyle through his mantra of Mission LIFE (lifestyle for the environment) and the world today moved in that direction. Despite the numerous various and unique concerns, the nations shown an extraordinary level of seriousness in their attempts to achieve a decisive victory on the matters affecting the battle against climate change. The research examines how the idea of sustainability is related to the country's climatic conditions and is descriptive in character. The paper is descriptive in nature and considers how the concept of sustainability is the essence of the country's well being. How the level of carbon emission is being calculated for different countries and the various risks associated with it. The basic objective of this study is to study how a developing country can be able to achieve the goal of carbon neutrality. What is the agenda of the COP summit and how do they contribute to achieving the path of sustainability?

Key Words: Carbon- Neutral, Sustainability, Climate change, COP Summit, Environment, Net-Zero, green bonds, Climate Finance.

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Introduction

Prime Minister Narendra Modi made a crucial speech in response to the UN Secretary-general's remarks. He declared emphatically that "we are excavating our coffins" by continuing to consume fossil fuels and urged people to cease "treating nature like a toilet." At the conference, US President Joe Biden remarked that "none of us can escape the worst of what's yet to come if we fail to grab this moment," while UK Prime Minister Boris Johnson said that future generations "will judge us with bitterness."

In recent times, governments across the globe have been trying to resolve the problems that arise due to climate change and become a dreadful threat to sustainability. For this purpose Govt. continuously focussing on the programmes associated with this issue. Some of the flagship programmes include United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the Paris Climate Change deal (2015) and Glasgow COP26 (2021). The 2015 U.N. Paris Agreement requires parties to revise their long-term climate objectives every five years, and as the effects of climate change deepen, parties are urged to be more ambitious.

At the Glasgow United Nations climate negotiations last year, Prime Minister Narendra Modi stated some objectives, but they were not yet defined. India committed to becoming carbon neutral by 2070 after reviewing the current situation and taking the Paris Agreement into account (COP 21). This is a crucial pledge that Mr. Modi made, one that must be fulfilled in the allotted time.

The level of carbon emission in today's scenario depicts there's a 50% probability that in the coming nine years the world will experience global warming limit of 1.5°C exceed, as per the analysis of global carbon emissions by scientists disclosed at the 27th Conference of Parties at Sharm El-Sheikh, Egypt. The government has also said it will aim for net zero emissions by 2070 - 20 years later than what climate scientists say is needed.

A sustainable way of living is the component we value the most. By including it in the strategy for combating climate change, the world today took a step in that direction. Through his campaign slogan, "Mission LIFE," Prime Minister Narendra Singh Modi has argued for leading a greener lifestyle (lifestyle for the environment). Despite the multiple unique and individual concerns, the countries have demonstrated considerable sincerity in their endeavours to make significant progress on all issues that affect the fight against climate change.

In terms of carbon dioxide emissions, China is now followed by India as the second largest emitter. The enormous population of India, which today faces stiff competition from China, as well as individual human irresponsibility, are both likely contributors to this. Global carbon emissions are predicted to increase by 1% over 2021 levels by 2022, according to the estimate (36.6 billion tones of CO₂). The authors who were present at COP 27 believe that we will not be able to keep global warming to 1.5°C as stipulated by the Paris Agreement. Currently, to achieve zero CO₂ emissions by 2050, a reduction of 1.4 GtCO₂ per year is required. This amount is equal to the observed decrease in 2020 emissions brought about by COVID-19 lockdowns.

Risks Associated with Climate Change

There are numerous types of risk that are present in the economy where climate risk is the deadliest one for present and future generations. Here, climate risk has a few defining characteristics that differentiate it from other risks. It has far-reaching, unpredictable, non-linear, and mostly irreversible consequences. Hazards associated with climate change and its mitigation, as well as its impact on the economy and financial implications, are considered to be climate-related risks. There are two main ways that it might affect the financial sector: physical hazards and transition risks. Analysing the cost-benefit parameters of the programmes related to reducing the impact of climate change, it has

become mandatory to analyse the related macroeconomic issues, including financial risks, geopolitical risks, trade policy and protectionism, changing global economic order, capital flows across borders, and international competitiveness of an economy or economies. There is a need arise to mitigate the risks arising out of extreme climate events that require a strong financial system to motivate the countries to approach the concept of green financing, keeping in mind the social and developmental objectives of the country.

It is critical to provide an efficient framework for identifying, evaluating, and managing this risk because it is one of the main threats to financial stability in both established and emerging nations. The risk that is assessed using an analysis of the probabilities, consequences, and reactions to the influence of climate change is known as financial risk associated with climate change. As a result, both the preventative actions and the actual climate change itself may raise financial issues. Globally, many investors are already starting to avoid "high-emitting sectors," or businesses, that have higher environmental costs or engage in activities that are likely to have a detrimental impact on the environment. Such a trend might result in a decrease in funding or an increase in financing costs for high-emitting organisations, which would make it uncertain if they could continue to operate. The Reserve Bank is striving to develop a strategy that takes into account its responsibilities and interests as a national institution as well as the top methods from across the globe for minimising the negative consequences of climate change. Another major factor in the rise of pollution is the idea of "greenwashing."

#	Country	CO2 Emissions (tons, 2016)	1 Year Change	Population (2016)	Per capita	Share of world
1	China	10,432,751,400	-0.28%	1,414,049,351	7.38	29.18%
2	United States	5,011,686,600	-2.01%	323,015,995	15.52	14.02%
3	India	2,592,830,100	4.71%	1,324,517,249	1.91	7.09%
4	Russia	1,661,899,300	-2.13%	145,275,383	11.44	4.65%
5	Japan	1,239,592,060	-1.21%	127,763,265	9.70	3.47%
6	Germany	775,752,190	1.28%	82,193,768	9.44	2.17%
7	Canada	675,918,610	-1.00%	36,382,944	18.58	1.89%
8	Iran	642,560,030	2.22%	79,563,989	8.08	1.80%
9	SOUTH Korea	604,043,830	0.45%	50,983,457	11.85	1.69%
10	Indonesia	530,035,650	6.41%	261,556,381	2.03	1.48%

(Source: Worldometer)

Climate Change Performance Index

Germanwatch is the organisation behind the Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI). It is a tool for encouraging openness in global climate change policy. It emphasises openness in global climate scenarios and contrasts it with national-level climatic conditions of various nations. It analyses their efforts and development with regard to the climate. 59 countries and the EU are evaluated and their climate performances are compared by the CCPI using a set of uniform criteria (as of CCPI 2023). These groupings account for more than 90% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (*CCPI website). There is open access to this index. It serves to serve as a reminder and an inspiration for the nations, and it fosters a sense of awareness and treating oneself as a responsible son of one's mother, the earth. Rankings of the countries clarify the complexity involved in recognising responsibilities and fulfilled and broken promises.

As India is in the top three, it has to do enough to prevent dangerous climate change. This means the country must be on track with its emissions development compared with the benchmark of well below 2°C and has set a 2030 GHG target, as CCPI uses a standardized framework to compare the climate performance. These standards are not met even by Denmark, the CCPI front-runner. At the 11th Summit of the Parties (COP 11) climate change conference in Montreal in 2005, this measure was initially introduced at the national and international levels. The backdrop at the international press conference at COP 13 in Bali makes it evident how important it is, where the index was only briefly introduced, there was already news coverage from more than 100 nations. Since the release of the CCPI in 2018, this index has periodically checked to see if nations are correctly setting their targets and keeping their commitments from the Paris climate summit. Mostly CCPI index consists of quantitative data, including the data related to Emissions of greenhouse and various other energy use categories. The data is taken from the International Energy Agency (IEA), PRIMAP (The PRIMAP-hist dataset integrates a number of freely accessible datasets to produce a thorough collection of greenhouse gas emission pathways for nations and Kyoto Gas, covering the years 1750–2019 and all UNFCCC United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) member nations. a UNFCCC region The principal IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) issues are addressed by this data) 2006 categories. The land use, land-use change and forestry (LULUCF) data contained in version 2.3.1 of the PRIMAP-hist dataset should be used with particular caution due to data availability and methodological issues), the Food and Agriculture Organization, and the national GHG inventories submitted to the UNFCCC. Since most data is only accessible two years after recording, the data year is always two years previous to index publishing. However, his GHG emissions data for 2021 (calculated using mathematical techniques and linear extrapolation) are used in CCPI 2023.

Each year, detailed questionnaires are used to gather data for the climate policy category. As a result, experts in climate and energy policy from NGOs, academic institutions, and think tanks in the nations that make up the categories evaluate the effectiveness of the policies.

The graph compares each country's progress toward fulfilling the Paris Agreement and its 2030 objective, showing how each one has performed over the previous few years. The data year is always two years prior to index publication because most data isn't available until two years after being recorded. He did, however, apply mathematical methods and linear extrapolation to produce the GHG emissions statistics for 2021, which were then incorporated in the CCPI 2023.

The graphic below shows the components involved in the CCPI index. It aims to deliver a detailed and 360° evaluation of the diverse countries at climate parameters. It considers 14 indicators (outer circle) under the following domains:

1. **GHG Emissions** (40% of overall score)
2. **Renewable Energy** (20% of overall score)
3. **Energy Use** (20% of overall score)
4. **Climate Policy** (20% of overall score)

India's Possible Gains from Transition to a Net Zero-Carbon Growth Path

India is one of the 185 countries that have ratified the Paris Agreement to combat climate change. In its nationally determined contribution (NDC), India promises a reduction in the emissions intensity of between 33 and 35%. (i.e. emissions for each unit of economic output by 2030 compared to 2005 levels). India aims to have 40% of its installed electrical capacity originate from nuclear or renewable sources by 2030. Large hydropower and other

renewable energy sources will have a combined installed capacity of 163 GW by August 31, 2022. The installed capacity for renewable is as follows:

- The following sources of energy make up the remaining GW: wind power (41.2 GW), solar power (59.34 GW), biomass (10.2 GW), small hydropower (4.88 GW), waste to energy (0.47 GW), and large hydropower (46.85 GW).
- India aims to attain net-zero carbon emissions by 2070 and 50% cumulative installed electric power by 2030, as well as a reduction in the economy's carbon intensity to under 45% by the end of the decade.
- The amount of new coal that will actually be generated in India as well as how frequently existing plants will operate are constantly up for debate due to the falling prices of renewable energy sources and the slower-than-expected rise in electricity consumption.
- A recent study revealed that a significant portion of the new coal plants might be abandoned. Forecasts for how the demand for coal in India would change have regularly been revised lower. According to India's climate commitment, 70% of its people rely on traditional biomass energy, which is inefficient and significantly increases indoor air pollution. Instead, India is promoting the use of biomass, which it claims is greener and more effective, to create electricity. The renewable energy park, a 30 GW solar-wind hybrid project, is being installed in Gujarat, which is the world's largest.

A Path Way by The Indian Government to Become Carbon Neutral

1. Green Bonds: Gaining momentum

Climate change mitigation is one of the many environmental benefits that green bonds, a type of financing instrument, can fund. However, so far, green bond projects haven't always resulted in

nearly the same level of carbon emissions as businesses. Here, as a complement to the current effort based on green labelling, we evaluate the potential benefits of a corporate-level score based on carbon intensity. In our view, such a score machine ought to serve as a positive signal to investors and serve as an incentive for businesses to reduce their carbon impact.

As a general term, "green finance" can be used to refer to financial investments made in projects and initiatives for sustainable development, environmental products, and policies that assist the development of a more sustainable economy. A wider range of "other environmental objectives" are also included, such as the preservation of biodiversity or the reduction of industrial pollution. The funding for mitigation and adaptation is particularly pertinent to climate change-related efforts. While financial flows for adaptation are related to investments that assist reduce the effects of climate change on commodities and people. Investments in projects and programmes that contribute to the reduction or eradication of greenhouse gas emissions are referred to as "mitigation of financial flows" (GHGs).

From a conceptual standpoint, "green finance" can be characterized as the financing of investments that have a positive influence on the environment within the context of more extensive environmentally sustainable development. These environmental benefits include things like reduced air, water, and land pollution, decreased greenhouse gas emissions, and increased energy efficiency. This idea is clear in its direction even though different nations may interpret it differently on a technical level. Interest in green bonds and green finance is rising in particular since it is now a primary priority for many issuers, asset managers, and governments.

Global average of avoided emissions intensity for green bond project activities, tCO₂e per \$1M invested

Data as of Sept. 12, 2022.

tCO2e = ones of carbon dioxide-equivalent

Source: 2022 Trucost Green Bond Dataset, S&P Global Sustainable1

The Trucost Green Bond allows investors to verify whether the positive impact produced by the green bond is consistent with what was anticipated at issuance by tracking the green bond's use of proceeds and impact on climate (carbon) over the course of the bond. Scores from the dataset are also included, which can be useful to fund managers when choosing green bonds.

The journey toward net zero is still a long one. According to the IPCC, it will take \$3.5 trillion in investments every year to keep global warming to 1.50 C above preindustrial levels by 2050. The availability of transparent and high-quality comparable data will facilitate this shift, and green bonds will be a potent weapon in it.

Green bonds as a tool against climate change? Serena Fatica Roberto Panzica 2020, JRC Working Papers in Economics and Finance, 2020/10 explained green bond issuers show a decline in the carbon intensity of their assets after borrowing from the green segment, compared to conventional bond issuers with comparable financial features and environmental ratings. When we remove green bonds used for refinancing, the decrease in emissions is more

pronounced, significant, and long-lasting. This is consistent with an increase in the number of climate-friendly activities brought on by new projects. In the case of green bonds that have an external evaluation and those issued after the Paris Agreement, we also observe a greater reduction in emissions.

1. Climate Finance

Climate finance is a component of green finance, although it is not the only one. Climate change mitigation and adaptation measures are supported by local, national, or transnational money that is obtained from a number of sources of gathering funds. The parties to the Convention, Kyoto Protocol and Paris Agreement are required to provide financial support to those who are less wealthy and more vulnerable. This acknowledges the wide variations in how much each country contributes to climate change and how well-equipped they are to stop it and deal with its effects. Since considerable emissions reduction calls for large-scale investments, climate finance is necessary for mitigation. Due to the considerable financial resources required to mitigate the negative consequences and adapt to a changing climate, climate finance is equally vital for adaptation.

However, India's efforts must be supported by the availability of climate finance from developed countries. Without foreign capital in concessional terms, this transition will prove difficult. The implications of a Net-zero Target for India's Sectoral Energy Transitions and Climate Policy report by the Council on Energy, Environment and Waters predict that for India to reach net-zero by 2070, installed solar power capacity must expand to more than 5,600 Gigawatts, the use of coal, particularly for the production of electricity, would need to decrease by 99% by 2060. Crude oil consumption would need to reach its peak in all sectors by 2050 and then drastically decline by 90% between 2050 and 2070. Green hydrogen could contribute 19% of the total energy needs of the industrial sector. The various other initiatives launched by India:

1. sovereign green bonds should be issued in public sector initiatives
2. Thermal power stations will co-fire 5-7% biomass pellets, reducing carbon dioxide emissions by 38 MMT yearly.
3. 59 solar parks have been approved in India with a combined capacity of 40 GW;
4. Solar Parks of 7 GW capacity in Pavagada, Kurnool, and Bhadla-II are included in the top 5 operational solar parks of the nation;
5. India gives a good platform for better opportunities for investments in the RE sector; **Union Budget 2022 Highlights**
6. Additional funding of INR 19,500 cr. For the solar PLI Program

2. Other guidelines issued by GOI

1. The development of methods on vulnerability and adaptation at all levels, as well as capacity-building for the inclusion of adaptation concerns in sustainable development initiatives, should be encouraged through effective and result-based measures.
2. Considering that economic development is necessary for the adoption of policies and for addressing the issue of climate change, policies and for the protection of the climate system against change made by human beings should be appropriate for the specific conditions of each party and should be considered with various national development and awareness programmes.
3. We should promote and focus on sustainable development.
4. To achieve sustainable development, and all parties shall continue to move forward with the implementation of their commitments to address climate change and its negative

effects. This is done while considering their common but differentiating responsibilities as well as their unique national and regional development priorities, objectives, and circumstances.

5. For developing nations, adapting to the negative effects of climate change is a top concern that requires immediate attention and action from the international community.

Key points to be highlighted in COP27

- 1) Countries agreed to establish a historic loss and damage fund

India would be one of the beneficiaries of this fund as it is primarily meant for the most vulnerable countries. India has many vulnerable sensitive areas. These funds support developing countries that are particularly vulnerable to the adverse effects of climate change. Institutional arrangements established for averting, minimising and addressing loss and damage associated with the adverse effect of climate change.

- 2) The enhancement in the investment of green renewable hydrogen forum
- 3) Introduction of a new insurance system called Global Shield is implemented to provide financial aid to vulnerable nations badly affected by climate change. This system initially receives revenue of €200 mn of funding.
- 4) It is announced initiate a new five-year work programme to promote climate technology solutions in developing counties.
- 5) UNSG Antorio Guterres announces \$ 3.1 bn to ensure everyone on the planet is protected by early warning systems within the next 5 years.
- 6) US Environmental Protection Agency announced to expansion of its 2021 methane rule, and reduce methane

from the oil & gas industry by 87% below the 2005 level.

- 7) Significant progress has been made in protecting forests with the launch of the Forest and Climate Leaders Partnership, which aims to join the efforts of governments, businesses and community leaders to end deforestation and land degradation by 2030.

Conclusion

COP on climate change is an annual agenda that is attended by representatives from almost every country on the planet, where global climate change prevention goals are negotiated, individual countries' plans to achieve those goals are presented, and progress is reported. Here, the Researcher tried to establish a connection between this summit and its impact on climate change. No doubt these are good approaches but still a focused and planned strategy is required for sustainability. The governments are coming up with numerous approaches and also implementing them with full enthusiasm but instead, all the climatic conditions keep deteriorating. The various authors have different viewpoints regarding this. In this COP-27 various countries have participated to have a discussion over rapidly changing climatic conditions. One of the examples is the recent rainfall in Indonesia which faced a severe level of rainfall and a huge loss. So it can be said that sound and effective policies should be implemented towards the achievement of the goal of sustainability.

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DATA PROTECTION VIS-À-VIS RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN INDIA

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Abstract

A person has the right to be free from interference into matters of a personal nature, which is sometimes referred to as the right to privacy. The ability to establish a domain around ourselves that encompasses all of the things that are a part of us, including as our body, home, property, ideas, feelings, secrets, and identity is included in the right to privacy. This right also includes the option to keep this domain private. The Supreme Court of India has established that an individual's right to privacy is a basic right, and at the same time, it has broadened the application of Article 21. The right to one's own privacy is one of the most fundamental rights, one that is essential to one's autonomy and the maintenance of human dignity. It enjoys protection under the terms of a number of international treaties. It is necessary for the maintenance of human dignity and is one of the fundamental principles that underpin a democratic state. It is an advocate for one's own rights as well as the rights of others. Everyone who is a human being automatically possesses the right to enjoy some degree of personal privacy. In addition to this, it involves the freedom to think and move freely, as well as to maintain one's physical integrity and individual autonomy. This suggests that privacy extends beyond the confines of the body and involves other aspects as well, such as integrity, personal autonomy, data, voice, permission, objections, movements, ideas, and reputation.

Keywords: Privacy Judiciary, Human Rights, Individual, Right.

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Introduction

The concept of privacy extends much beyond the act of secluding oneself in a room; it encompasses the non-disclosure of private information, original works, trade secrets, personal relationships and life, and other facets of one's life. If a person's letters to another are published without that person's permission, it is a breach of that person's right to privacy. The potential for technology to be abused grows steadily larger as our society moves in the direction of ever-increasing technological sophistication. Because there are no explicit or strong rules for data protection in India, the country is seeing a spike in the number of cybercrimes that are committed on a daily basis. The purpose of data protection is to ensure the confidentiality of an individual's personal information.

The right to one's own privacy is not made crystal clear or explicitly stated in the Constitution of India; rather, it is left open to judicial interpretation. The right to privacy has been included within the purview of the basic right as a result of the judicial interpretation of the fundamental rights¹.

In Indian jurisprudence, the "Right to Privacy" can be traced back to the late 1800s, when it was upheld by a British local court that the privacy of a Pardanashin woman to go to her balcony without any fear of anyone gazing at her from the neighbourhood was protected. At the time, this meant that the woman could go to her balcony without worrying that anyone in the neighbourhood would look at her inappropriately. Even though the right to privacy is not expressly recognised by the Constitution of India, this body of law has developed since Article 21 of the Indian Constitution first mentioned the right to private. According to Article 21², "No individual shall be deprived of his life or personal liberty unless according to the method established by law," no one can be taken away from their life or personal freedom.

¹ Article 21 of the Indian Constitution Act, 1950.

² The Indian Constitution Act, 1950.

The Data Protection Mechanism in India

India is not a technologically advanced country, but it has embraced the digital era, raising data privacy worries. Data is a branch or topic's information. Data protection began with data acquisition and possession. India currently has no data protection law or regulation. Certain laws and actions tackle this topic. The Indian Constitution protects data privacy through its golden triangle³. The Supreme Court has held that Article 21 protects a citizen's private data as private property. Article 21⁴ protects one's data. Section 27⁵ allows parties to include a data-protection clause in their contracts. The Information Technology Act, 2000 intends to establish a legal framework for the digital era, including e-commerce platforms, electronic contracts, e-mails, online banking, etc. After so many years, the digital age has progressed greatly. Many internet venues have expanded the IT Act's relevance. This Act protects data. It provides a legal framework to stop database misuse and hefty cybercrime penalties. After 2008, it added data protection and privacy regulations⁶. Sections 43 (a), (b), and 7⁷ section penalises accessing a secure computer network without the owner's permission, downloading, copying, or extracting data from the computer, and stealing, concealing, destroying, or altering computer source or data purposefully to cause damage. The perpetrator must pay at least 1 crore to the victim or owner. It indicates plainly that any corporate entity handling or possessing sensitive personal data or information in its computer did not establish an appropriate security system and lost or shared the data. If a corporation's negligence causes unjust loss or gain, it must pay damages of at least 5 crore rupees⁸. The government notified these

³ Articles 14, 19 and 21 of the Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

⁴ The Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

⁵ The Indian Contract Act, 1872

⁶ The Information Technology (Amendment) Act, 2008.

⁷ The Information Technology Act, 2000.

⁸ Section 43 of the Information Technology Act, 2000.

rules for sensitive personal data in 2011. Companies and corporations must observe certain regulations while managing sensitive information. Rule 4⁹ requires corporate bodies or a person on their behalf to collect, receive, and handle information from the provider. They must offer a privacy policy for managing sensitive information and ensure the information is under a legal contract. Policy should be posted online. Companies and other corporate organisations shall not gather sensitive or personal data without the owner's written authorization.¹⁰ If a corporation obtains sensitive or personal information, it must build a security system. Clause 2 of this rule cites an ISO security standard for data protection, although it's not required if they utilise a better system.¹¹ Section 66 C¹² punishes identity theft with 3 years in prison and a 200,000 rupee fine. So, anyone who fraudulently uses another's electronic signature, password, or unique identity will be punished. The Copyright Act¹³, as revised, recognises computer databases as literary works, hence copying them is a criminal offence. It safeguards literary, theatrical, artistic, etc. IP rights. The task involves the computer's database. Copying a computer database and distributing it is copyright infringement, which can lead to legal and criminal penalties. As intellectual property, the statute protects data and databases. Under the Copyright Act¹⁴, database and data protection are difficult to distinguish. Data protection protects a person's private information, whereas database protection protects a work's originality, effort, and presentation.

Judicial Interpretation in Protecting Right to Privacy in India

The Indian courts speaking through its honourable judges has time and again upheld the right to privacy as one of the most sacrosanct

⁹ Sensitive Personal Data Information Rules, 2011.

¹⁰ Rule 5 of the Sensitive Personal Data Information Rules, 2011.

¹¹ Rule 8 of the Sensitive Personal Data Information Rules, 2011

¹² The Information Technology Act, 2000.

¹³ The Copyright Act, 1957.

¹⁴ Act of 1957.

fundamental right of the citizens. The apex court and the high courts have valued the most sought after fundamental right of the citizens and non-citizens residing within the territorial jurisdiction of India.

In the case of *M.P. Sharma and Ors. v. Satish Chandra, District Magistrate, Delhi and Ors.*¹⁵, the apex court for the first time came up with the question whether right to privacy is a fundamental right or not for search and seizure warrant under Sections 94 & 96(1)¹⁶? The court ruled that to protect social security, search and seizure is mandatory and does not violate the fundamental right. In the case of *Kharak Singh v. State of Uttar Pradesh and Ors.*¹⁷, the question was whether the accused's night time home surveillance violated Article 21¹⁸ of the Indian Constitution. The Supreme Court ruled that the visit violated Article 21¹⁹. The majority of judges said Article 21²⁰ doesn't include privacy, so it's not a basic right. Such surveillance doesn't breach Article 19 (1)(d)²¹, and the right to privacy isn't guaranteed. Watching the suspect's movements does not violate Part III of the constitution. In the case of *Govind v. State of Madhya Pradesh*²², the Supreme Court ruled that police regulations did not respect a person's personal freedom and that the right to privacy is a fundamental right that should be assessed case by case. The famous case of *R. Rajagopal and Anr. v. State of Tamil Nadu (Auto-Shanker Case)*²³ explained the evolution and breadth of privacy rights. The Supreme Court, after considering the jurisprudence, extent, and growth of the right to privacy in

¹⁵ 1954 AIR 300, 1954 SCR 1077

¹⁶ The Criminal Procedure Code, 1973.

¹⁷ 1963 AIR 1295, 1964 SCR (1) 332

¹⁸ The Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

¹⁹ The Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

²⁰ The Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

²¹ The Indian Constitution Act, 1949.

²² 1975 AIR 1378, 1975 SCR (3) 946

²³ 1995 AIR 264, 1994 SCC (6) 632

Govind's case, ruled that it is a part of the right to life and personal liberty provided by Article 21 and not only a matter of public record. In the case of *People's Union for Civil Liberties (PUCL) v. Union of India*²⁴, the question was whether phone tapping violates privacy. The Supreme Court ruled that phone calls are private and confidential, violating the right to privacy. Including the right to privacy under Article 21 depends on the facts. In the popular case of *Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) and Anr. v. Union of India and Ors.*²⁵, this is a significant case since the Supreme Court ruled that Articles 14, 19, and 21 of the Indian Constitution protect the right to privacy. This overturned Kharak Singh and M.P. Sharma.

Data Privacy Issues in Indian Perspective

In India, many people are still debating whether the country should switch from its current model, which is based on permission, to one that is rights-based. In the present model that is based on consent, the data controller is granted permission to process and distribute the data once it has received the user's written approval to do so. However, a large number of people provide their agreement without fully understanding the implications of their actions. Whereas, according to the right-based model, it grants the users an increasing number of rights over their data, and it is the responsibility of the data controller to make sure that these rights are not violated in any way. In the event that there is a data breach, citizens now have the legal right to seek court remedies thanks to a ruling made by the Honourable Supreme Court. Because of this, it is possible that this will have an effect on the laws and regulations that are adopted by the technology businesses, as the users now have the ability to not only file tort-based claims but also invoke their basic right to privacy. The Honourable Supreme Court has ruled that in order to safeguard the interests of the state, it is permissible for the state to interfere with or infringe upon a citizen's

²⁴ AIR 1997 SC 568, JT 1997 (1) SC 288, 1996 (9) SCALE 318,

²⁵ AIR 2018

fundamental rights. However, before passing a law that aims to infringe upon fundamental rights, there is a need to examine whether or not the law is reasonable and whether or not it is proportional.

Necessity for Having a Rigid Data Protection Framework in India

There are many flaws in data protection legislation must be closed. The IT Act only covers data gathering and processing by ‘body corporate.’ Other data isn’t protected. This doesn’t protect sensitive public data. When Aadhaar is linked to personal information, it remains confidential and is shared with the Income Tax Department, but the Income Tax Act does not protect the data. The Personal Data Protection Bill gives the Data Protection Authority unlimited ability to arrest or detain a person without court approval. The PDPB law has no deadline for reporting a data breach. Complaints can only be filed when harm is done, therefore they don’t prevent data breaches. The measure hasn’t passed, but it could give the government free access to citizen data. The bill allows the State to process data without consent. This is nonsensical because even State representatives can tamper with data and utilise it illegally. In India, there’s no minimum age for joining social media networks that are prone to data breaches.

Suggestive Measures for Having A Robust Data Privacy Framework In India

In addition to regulations for the reasonable and fair collection of data, the Personal Data Protection bill should also specify rules for the reasonable and fair processing of data by the data fiduciaries. This should be included alongside the rules for the reasonable and fair collection of data. The vague concept of incidental objectives found in Section 5 of the PDPB bill has to be clarified in a comprehensive manner. In the interest of maintaining complete openness, data fiduciaries should be forced to acknowledge any data breaches on their own websites. The General Data Protection

Regulation requires that people's constitutionally protected rights to personal privacy be accorded a high priority, and this should be done (GDPR). For the sake of maintaining openness in the event of a data breach, the data authority should make the data protection effect estimation and data audits available to the general public. Even if the bill addresses all of the main principles, it still needs more work on the permission of the people in case there are exceptions, and it also needs to work on protecting the privacy of the information.

Conclusion

Despite the fact that India is striving toward the development and creation of legislation for data protection and privacy, there are still some loopholes that need to be focused upon. As a result, our Indian legislature has to include the positive aspects of the data protection and privacy laws from across the world and take a step forward in the creation of this new branch of legislation due to the fact that it is of the utmost importance in the times in which we live. There are many different laws for data protection around the world, and if India were to adopt and strictly follow some of these rules, it might help to reduce the number of problems that are associated with data protection.

The Indian courts speaking through its honourable judges has time and again upheld the right to privacy as one of the most sacrosanct fundamental right of the citizens. The apex court and the high courts have valued the most sought after fundamental right of the citizens and non-citizens residing within the territorial jurisdiction of India.

MEDICAL TOURISM AND THE LAW IN INDIA

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Abstract

Medical tourism refers to patients travelling voluntarily to another nation for private medical treatment. It can take various forms and types which has been discussed in the paper. India is growing to become the top destination for medical tourism around the globe and is comparatively positioned on a higher pedestal in this area than most of the countries. However, along with being extremely helpful and positively impactful on the growth of the host country, medical tourism and the practices involved thereof are subject to legal and ethical issues which can have a significant negative effect on the world as a whole. In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the stance of medical tourism and where it stands with the law in India particularly. The legal and ethical aspects of medical tourism have also been discussed in the second half of the paper although data on the viability of ethical issues is limited.

1. Introduction

The tourism industry is considered to be one of the fastest growing and thriving industries around the globe. In the recent past years, the growth of this industry is not only confined to hotels, rejuvenation, monuments, etc. but also extends to the health care services, which is commonly known as medical tourism.

Medical tourism can be defined as when consumers across the world choose to travel across international borders along with an intention of receiving a certain form of medical treatment. In simpler words, it refers to the phenomenon wherein one person travels to another country for the purpose of acquiring some type of

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medical care or treatment. Such treatment may cover all types of medical services, but is most commonly seen in dental care, cosmetic surgery, fertility treatment, et cetera.

The business of medical tourism is seen to be as quite promising. As per the reports of Medical Tourist Association, around 14 million people engage in medical tourism on a global basis¹, i.e., travel from one country to another for the purpose of seeking some form of medical treatment. This industry is rapidly growing and exhibits promising profits since it is a fusion of two vast industries—medicine and tourism. The combination of the requirements of these two industries poses a great deal for medical tourism around the world, since people around the world travel to foreign countries for the purpose of acquiring medical care and alongside also enjoy the travel benefits that the host countries have to offer.

Nevertheless, if one investigates into the term ‘Medical Tourism’, it may come to seem as incongruous since it is invariably odd to couple two pole opposite concepts of tourism and medicine. While tourism is seen as an activity of voluntary leisure usually perceived as a time for luxurious enjoyment and substitute of the monotony of everyday life away from the frantic impediment that is associated with the normal routine of a person, it indeed stands in stark polarity of hospitalization, medical treatment, and the gloomy and depressing air that is seen in a hospital². In the eyes of normality, these two domains seem to be fairly incompatible with each other as tourism invokes a sense of enjoyment, freedom, and rejuvenation and hospital on the other end invokes feelings of grief, hardships, and trauma. In a utopian world, these two concepts will not mingle with one another³. But as bizarre as it may seem to be,

¹ <https://www.fortunebusinessinsights.com/industry-reports/medical-tourism-market-100681>

² Graburn, N. H. (1977). *Tourism: The sacred journey*. In V. L. Smith, *Hosts and Guests* (pp. 17-31). Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press.

³ Ross. (2001, September 6). *Medical check-ups on the run*. Bangkok Post, Horizons, p. 3.

the medical tourism industry is flourishing and gaining traction due to the fact that consumers who are under insured or do not own any sort of medical insurance in their own country fly to the under developed nations to seek the medical treatment they require and reap the benefits of the law which they may not attain in their own country.

It can be undeniably agreed that Medical Tourism has gained recognition and immense acceptance across the world and is definitely not a recent phenomenon. Furthermore, as per recent reports, it is estimated that by the year 2023, the global market for medical tourism may exceed a figure of 180 billion US dollars since the capability of advantageous patients travelling from their wealthy countries to developing nations which have a booming healthcare framework is increasing rapidly⁴. There are adequate statistics to prove that the medical tourism market is progressing toward great heights. It is also being followed by various citizens around the globe. In a very recent news article dated 28th October, 2022, it has been observed that looking at the picture in terms of volume, an estimated number of approximately 23,042 patients accounted for the global market and the same is expected to reach a figure of 70,358 patients by the year 2027 alongside a compound annual growth rate of an augmenting 15% from 2019 to 2027⁵.

Taking in consideration the staggering progress projected by the medical tourism market over the years, is there a possibility that such an industry can hamper the economic growth of both the nations involved namely the host country (the one providing the medical services) and the home country (the resident country of the patient seeking assistance)? Can the so called flourishing global

⁴ <https://www.glasgowinsights.com/events/medical-tourism-market-could-boom-to-180-billion-by-2025/>

⁵ <https://knoxreports.com/medical-tourism-market-revenue-to-rise-substantially-owing-to-increasing-end-use-adoption/>

market have an ill-impact on the national healthcare framework of the countries? Further, is of medical tourism ethical and moral in terms of the lawfulness expected by the citizens of a nation?

In this paper, the author has attempted to draw upon the various facets of medical tourism and the challenges it may bring therewith to both the host nation and the home nation, placing special focus on the Indian subcontinent and its role in Medical Tourism vis a vis the legal framework existing in India.

2. Why Medical Tourism?

Before getting into looking at the advantages and disadvantages that are attached to medical tourism, it is essential to have a look at the reasons responsible for medical tourism in the first place.

There are several reasons for the development of medical tourism, although the list not being an exhaustive one. As per various different scholars and compiled by Hall in his work⁶, there are five potential reasons for medical tourism:

- a) For monetary reasons meaning thereby the reduction in the cost of the medical treatment so required by the patient. The patient here chooses to opt for a cross border medical service since the cost of the said treatment is cheaper and more easily and timely available in another country as compared to its resident country. This theory is known as economic cost dimension⁷.
- b) For simultaneous pleasure-seeking reasons meaning thereby

⁶ C. Michael Hall, (2011), "Health and medical tourism: a kill or cure for global public health?", *Tourism Review*, Vol. 66 Iss 1/2 pp. 4 - 15

⁷ Milstein, A. and Smith, M. (2006), "America's new refugees – seeking affordable surgery offshore", *New England Journal of Medicine*, Vol. 355 No. 16, pp. 1637-40.

the travel for the purposes of receiving medical is coupled with a vacation. Here, the patient's purpose to visit another country is not solely confined to the seeking of medical care but is also open to gratifying pleasure and undergoing a vacation. This theory is known as the commercial behavior dimension⁸.

- c) Restricted to the immigrants, the activity of medical tourism is done for options none other than familial, cultural, or linguistic reasons. Here, the patients (specifically migrant workers or immigrants in general) return to their place of origin for seeking medical treatment. This theory is termed as non-commercial behavior dimension⁹.
- d) For reasons of legality meaning thereby the medical treatment so demanded by the patient is not legal in their home country. Thus, the patient here would travel to another country for seeking some medical assistance which is legal in a country other than its own. Taking a very recent example, the practice of abortion being criminalized by virtue of an off-late Supreme Court decision¹⁰ overturning the landmark judgement of *Roe v. Wade*¹¹ in the United States of America, an American woman, if wanting to abort, may choose to travel to countries like India, Australia, Singapore, etc. wherein the practice is legal and feasible. Further, the issues of fertility

⁸ Connell, J. (2006), "Medical tourism: sea, sun, sand and ... surgery", *Tourism Management*, Vol. 27, pp. 1093-100.

⁹ Lee, J.Y., Kearns, R.A. and Friesen, W. (2010), "Seeking affective health care: Korean immigrants' use of homeland medical services", *Health and Place*, Vol. 16 No. 1, pp. 108-15.

¹⁰ *vide* *Dobbs v. Jackson Women's Health Organization*, No. 19-1392, 597 U.S. ____ (2022).

¹¹ 410 U.S. 113 (1973)

and reproduction tourism¹², stem cell tourism¹³, et cetera would also fall under this category. This theory is termed as regulatory cost dimension¹⁴.

- e) And last but not the least, for reasons of unavailability of organs required for treatment, meaning thereby that the home country is not able to meet the needs of requirement of the distressed patient. Here, the patient would have to travel across border only to obtain organs that are available for donation. This reason is considered to be problematic since it carries with it some potential illegal and immoral consequences such as organ trafficking¹⁵.

As pointed out before, these dimensions are indeed not mutually absolute and with the changing trends and needs of the world, the requirements of such tourism may keep on changing. Some other reasons for medical tourism could be demographic dimension, availability of non-conventional and alternative forms of medication like Homeopathy, or many more.

The following part of the paper centrally focuses on the fourth

¹² Bergmann, S. (2011), "Fertility tourism: circumventive routes that enable access to reproductive technologies and substances", *Signs*, Vol. 36 No. 2, pp. 280-9; Shenfield, F., de Mouzon, J., Pennings, G., Ferraretti, A.P., Nyboe Andersen, A., De Wert, G. and Goossens, V. (2010), "Cross border reproductive care in six European countries", *Human Reproduction*, Vol. 25 No. 6, pp. 1361-8.

¹³ MacReady, N. (2009), "The murky ethics of stem-cell tourism", *The Lancet Oncology*, Vol. 10 No. 4, pp. 317-8.

¹⁴ Gilmartin, M. and White, A. (2011), "Comparative perspectives symposium: gender and medical tourism interrogating medical tourism: Ireland, abortion, and mobility rights", *Signs*, Vol. 36 No. 2, pp. 275-80

¹⁵ Bramstedt, K.A. and Xu, J. (2007), "Checklist: passport, plane ticket, organ transplant", *American Journal of Transplantation*, Vol. 7 No. 7, pp. 1698-701; Scheper-Hughes, N. (2003), "Keeping an eye on the global traffic in human organs", *Lancet*, Vol. 361 No. 9369, pp. 1645-8.

dimension of medical tourism which relates itself to the legal facet and how the legal framework of nations is responsible for the surfacing of the medical tourism, specifically India being a party to the tourism activity. We will take a look at how medical tourism occurs due to the medical practices being illegal in the home countries forcing the patient to travel internationally and seek the same for their personal gratification.

2.1 Types of Medical Tourism

Medical Tourism is classified into two types, namely incoming/inbound and outgoing/outbound. While the former kind of medical tourism deals with when the nations act as a receiver of international patients for medical treatment, on the other hand, the latter kind of medical tourism refers to the patient's country of origin which has been left behind for varying reasons. Therefore, taking the example of India, incoming or inbound tourism would be when a foreigner travels to India in order to receive medical care, whereas outgoing or outbound medical tourism, which is the opposite, would mean that patients from India are travelling abroad to seek medical care.

It is only natural that for India or any country for that matter, both kinds of medical tourism would have their pros and cons. As per reports and statistics, India is among the top ten destinations across the world for Medical Tourism¹⁶.

2.2 India as a top-destination for Medical Tourism

India is definitely one of the most popular destinations for the medical tourism. In fact, India is estimated to become the largest hub for medical tourism wherein the trend started to gain

¹⁶ James E Dalen and Joseph S. Alpert "Medical Tourists: Incoming and Outgoing Dalen", *The American Journal of Medicine*, Volume 132, Issue 1, 9–10.

momentum from the last decade, and in present day as per latest reports, India sustains about 2 million patients belonging to foreign countries thereby producing a foreign exchange value of 4 billion, annually¹⁷.

But it doesn't stop here since with the efforts undertaken by the Government of India and specifically the Union Health Ministry (headed by Mr. Mansukh Mandaviya), India is expected to become the No.1 destination for receiving medical care and the forex value is expected to go three times the current generating value. As per the Ministry of Tourism, Bureau of Immigration, the number of foreign tourists visiting India has been on an increase ranging from 4,27,000 in the year 2016, 4,95,000 in 2017, 6,41,000 in 2018, reaching up to 6,97,000 in 2019, but going down to 1,83,000 in the year 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic¹⁸. Although the pandemic has had a negative effect on the medical tourism industry, it is appurtenant to note that the inflow of foreign patients is rapidly increasing again post COVID-19¹⁹. Further, specific private hospital chains are also seeing a greater influx of foreign patients wanting to receive medical treatment in India²⁰.

¹⁷ Danish Ahmed. "India to emerge as largest destination for medical tourism" *The Times of India*, May 2022. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/medical-tourism-destination-india/>

¹⁸ Shantanu Nandan Sharma. "Medicine Sans Frontiers: India is gearing up to grab a larger pie of \$80-bn medical tourism market" *The Economic Times*, July 2022. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/healthcare/biotech/healthcare/medicine-sans-frontiers-india-is-gearing-up-to-grab-a-larger-pie-of-80-bn-medical-tourism-market/articleshow/92924586.cms>

¹⁹ <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/healthcare/biotech/healthcare/medical-tourism-sector-getting-back-in-health-with-higher-inflow-of-patients-than-pre-covid-times/articleshow/93089851.cms>

²⁰ <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/industry/healthcare/biotech/healthcare/hospital-chains-witness-a-revival-in-medical-tourism/articleshow/89600484.cms>

Thus, it is needless to state that India is on its way to become one of the biggest medical tourism hubs in the world.

2.2.1 Why India?

India being a culture focused country, provides an amalgamation of traditional and modern medical care which makes India unique in the industry. Along with having a world class array of medical professionals and the prices at which the care is being provided is substantially low as compared to the other competing countries of the industry. By incorporating some of the oldest medical practices i.e., AYUSH, India finds itself to be in a position higher than other countries with low cost of medical care as well²¹.

3. Legal Aspects of Medical Tourism

As the medical tourism industry involves a combination of two industries i.e., health and tourism, the legal facet of the same cannot be left behind and becomes extremely important given the fact that it involves participants from two different countries.

3.1 Legal Arrangement in India

As it has been well established hereinbefore that India holds a significantly high position in the medical tourism industry, and that the GOI has been taking significant measures to improve this position, there are certain facilities that have been introduced which corroborate the seriousness of the government to expand the medical tourism industry.

- a) The introduction of medical visas has been extremely helpful in facilitating the spread of medical tourism in India. These

²¹ Garg, D. R., Batra, R., & Banerji, A. (2020). Low Cost, Quality Treatment and Excellent Hospitality Makes India the Best Destination for Medical Tourism. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Medical Science*, 5(01), 10 to 15.

visas cater solely for availing medical services in India along with a requisite of a previous statement from a medical professional stating the need for specialized medical care and is valid for a period of one year²². Through the advent of these visas, fraudulent and frivolous requests for medical care can be avoided and thereby a duty is cast upon the hospitals to only receive a tourist if they have applied for such a visa or already possess one. It is quite possible that some people receive medical care with a mischievous intent which could thereof impact the growth and repute of Indian medical facilities altogether. However, in some cases where medical treatment is unforeseen, normal visas can also be converted into medical visas but obviously if it meets the required criteria²³.

- b) Further, the municipal medical malpractices laws can be applied and invoked in case of need. The Consumer Protection Act, 2019 allows consumers to file a consumer case in case they feel that their services have been unfair or there is a breach in services so provided. In India, a medical provider, medical professional, hospital, etc. all can be sued in case of negligence as per the established rules and precedents.

3.2 Legal and Ethical Issues involved

While there are various benefits of getting treated across borders, the same has its shortcomings. The aggrieved patients have to rely on international law (mainly treaties) and municipal law of the country they have travelled to for seeking medical assistance. The patients travelling across borders to seek medical care go in with an

²² <https://www.indiavisa-online.org/india-visa-types/medical-visa;>
<https://www.ima-india.org/ima/left-side-bar.php?pid=503>

²³ <https://legalformatsindia.com/the-legal-regime-of-medical-tourism-in-india/>

expectation of an above par character and in case there happens to be any setback by the medical care providers, it can go up to costing the patient's life. While there is no doubt that medical professionals are under oath and will naturally provide the highest achievable medical care, the unforeseen and unprecedented possibility of risks attached to medical practice must be borne by the patient beforehand. Moreso, the person travelling from their country of origin might be used to a different legal recourse system than that of the place of destination. This would obviously pose challenges for the aggrieved patient and there might be chances that they do not attain the verdict they expect to due to the different threshold of penalties and adjudication in different jurisdictions. Also, the costs to be borne by the person in case he/she chooses to opt for any legal action may also differ significantly from their country of origin and therefore cause further difficulties²⁴. Furthermore, a lack of a uniform and universal legislation or code on Medical Tourism indeed acts as an impediments for the patients in case there occurs any challenge whatsoever. This would automatically mean that the rights, duties, and responsibilities of both the participants i.e., the service providers and the receivers are not all-inclusive and may differ from country to country. Moreover, the lack of uniformity and universality in the area of the kind of medical devices and instruments to be used would inherently obstruct the regulation of any such malpractice and has the capability of creating a havoc across the world. For instance, the infamous PIP (Poly Implant Prothese) breast implant scare that took place in France is considered to be a classic example under medical tourism scandals.

Due to lack of a global regulation in medical tourism, there are high chances of patients travelling to another countries in order to seek a form of medical care which is not legal or acceptable in their country of origin (reason of regulatory cost dimensionas raised

²⁴ Storrow, R. F., "Assisted reproduction on treacherous terrain: The legal hazards of cross-border reproductive travel", *Reproductive BioMedicine Online*, 23(.5) (2011): 5

hereinbefore) under which an archetypal illustration is that of surrogacy and abortion. Here, the regulation and determination of any case would entirely depend on the municipal laws of the country where the medical treatment is being sought. In countries like Australia Georgia, etc., the practice of surrogacy is legal, and these countries would definitely receive patients from across borders wherein the practice of surrogacy is altogether prohibited by law (Countries such as Japan, Turkey, China, etc). In the case of India specifically, up until the year 2016, surrogacy tourism was a well-recognized practice. From the period of 2004 to 2010, a fertility clinic named Akanksha Infertility Clinic situated in the state of Gujarat had steered around 200 or more surrogate babies in the world²⁵ and as per the GOI, it was observed in a study published by the Confederation of Indian Industry that the medical tourism industry (inclusive of surrogacy tourism) is expected to generate 2.3 billion by 2012²⁶. Thus, it is established that surrogacy tourism was well practiced and even well received in the Indian subcontinent. However, such practices were put to a halt in 2016, when the practice of surrogacy was banned in India owing to the Surrogacy Regulation Bill which later became an act in the year 2021. Therefore, as of now, Indians living overseas, citizens of other countries, unmarried couples, single parents, same-sex couples do not have a choice for opting surrogacy in India. Thus, while in the year 2002, India legalized the concept of surrogacy with an aim to promote medical tourism, the current legal framework in India, which was previously receiving patients across borders for surrogacy, has now forced its citizens (who wish to opt for surrogacy) to travel to foreign countries where surrogacy is a legal practice.²⁷

²⁵ <https://www.motherjones.com/politics/2010/04/surrogacy-tourism-india-nayna-patel/>

²⁶ Bhowmick, Nilanjana. 2013. "Why People Are Angry about India's New Surrogacy Rules." *Time*, February 15. Accessed March 3, 2017. <http://world.time.com/2013/02/15/why-people-are-angry-about-indias-new-surrogacy-laws/>

²⁷ The author of this paper does not intend to promote cross border surrogacy or any form of surrogacy as a practice

It is noteworthy to mention that surrogacy tourism indeed gives rise to varied number of ethical issues such as in nationality of child born, rights of child, theory of treating the child as an object, et cetera²⁸. For instance, in the United Kingdom, for legal recognition of the baby, there is no mandate for adoption, whereas in Belgium, adoption is mandatory for the same²⁹. Nevertheless, it has been observed that medical tourism gives rise to various other ethical issues as well such as negative effect on the care provided to local residents of the country. One of the most cited ill-effects of medical tourism is that it would invariably lead to a degradation in the quality of care received by the citizen nationals of the host country³⁰.

Another case is that of abortion tourism which would be similar to surrogacy tourism except that herein, the patients choose to opt for abortion practice. After the infamous criminalizing of abortion in the USA, it is natural that women would travel cross borders to countries which do not prohibit abortion as a practice³¹. As per a recent news report, it was seen that a US national chose to opt for abortion soon after a week of overturning of *Roe v. Wade*³² by travelling across borders³³. Further, after another such instance of abortion tourism in the country of Malta by a US citizen has led to

²⁸ T A, Binoy. (2018). AN EVALUATION OF SURROGACY TOURISM IN INDIA. *International Journal of Current Research* Volume 10, Issue 02.

²⁹ Crockin SL. Growing families in a shrinking world: legal and ethical challenges in cross-border surrogacy. *Reprod Biomed Online*. 2013 Dec;27(6):733-41

³⁰ Wahed, H. (2015). Ethical and Legal Issues in Medical Tourism. *IJUM Law Journal*, 23(2); <https://journals.iium.edu.my/iiumlj/index.php/iiumlj/article/view/130/161>

³¹ <https://news.bloomberglaw.com/health-law-and-business/abortion-travel-bans-emerge-as-next-frontier-after-roes-end>

³² *supra* note 11

³³ See <https://www.vice.com/en/article/m7gx4v/abortion-missouri>

the authorities of Malta considering an application for a potential ban on abortion³⁴.

It was also seen that a mega number of citizens in USA protested the decision of the Supreme Court in snatching away the woman's constitutional right to abortion³⁵. However, again, such international travel (from countries that prohibit abortion) to avail abortion services in countries where it is legal to do so would give rise to multiple legal and ethical challenges and is definitely not the principled way out³⁶. In the case of India specifically, unlike surrogacy, abortion up to 20 weeks is legal and allowed for foreign nationals as well.³⁷

4. Conclusion

Medical tourism is a blend of two industries and refers to when a person travels across borders in order to avail medical services. It allows for quicker access to medical care and enables people the chance to get high-quality care that is not offered in their native nations at a lesser cost. The reasons for opting for Medical Tourism are manifold and have been discussed in the paper.

This industry is a growing one and has several benefits for the populace of both the countries i.e., host and receiver. India is predicted to continue to rise in popularity as one of the world's top destinations for medical tourists and is capable of becoming the largest hub for such kind of tourism.

³⁴ <https://www.france24.com/en/live-news/20220630-malta-to-review-application-of-abortion-ban-after-us-tourist-case>

³⁵ <https://www.nytimes.com/live/2022/06/24/us/roe-wade-abortion-supreme-court>

³⁶ ALYSON O'DANIEL, ELIZABETH ZIFF "International Travel to Access Abortion Is a Global Health Problem—Not a Solution" *Ms Magazine* (2022); <https://msmagazine.com/2022/06/03/international-travel-abortion-access/>

³⁷ the author of this paper does not intend to promote cross border abortion

However, the concept of medical tourism does not attach itself to any concrete, written, codified, or a uniform and universal law which is the reason it gives rise to various legal and ethical issues which have also been discussed thoroughly in the paper. By way of a uniform code or well established written international rules, the malpractices, legal and ethical issues can be controlled well within requirements. Therefore, as of present day, however beneficial medical tourism might be, a uniform code for the regulation of the same is the need of the hour to tackle the legal and ethical consequence it brings with itself.

COLLECTIVE INVESTMENT SCHEME: AN ANALYSIS

Aryan Sinha*

Abstract

A collective Investment Scheme (CIS) is a popular investment scheme in the securities market. In this, multiple people combine their money to invest in a specific asset(s) and share the profits as agreed upon before pooling the funds. Each investor has a proportional stake in the Collective Investment Scheme portfolio based on how much money they have contributed. Large-scale mis-utilization of funds and consequent fraudulent activities lead to the establishment-of a regulated system for the operation of CIS. A Committee was constituted under the Chairmanship of Dr. S. A. Dave to examine and finalize the draft for the regulation of the Collective investment scheme. And SEBI issued a collective investment scheme known as SEBI (collective investment schemes) Regulations 1996. In this research paper, we will be discussing the concept of CIS, its applicability under SEBI, History, Characteristics/Features of CIS, Exceptions, Registration, and conditions of Collective Investment Management Company (CIMC), Certificate of CIS, Trustee for CIS, Procedure for launching CIS, Action, and Penalties in case of default CIS.

Keywords: Collective Investment Schemes, SEBI, Collective Investment Management Company, Securities Law

Collective Investment Scheme: The Concept

We have heard about the collective efforts of an individual in a group for the betterment of the entire group. Similarly, the concept of CIS is based on this ideology. “Collective Investment Scheme

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(CIS) is a mechanism where several individuals mutually pool their money to invest it in a particular asset. Further, when profits are arising out of that particular investment, it gets shared between the investors as per the finalized agreement, before the act¹. This form of scheme is somehow similar to a mutual fund. However, it is not a mutual fund.

In more depth, “the collective investment scheme is a plan of action that comprises a pool of assets that are managed & handled by the collective scheme manager and is governed by the Collective Investment Schemes Regulations issued by the Securities & Exchange Board of India. Thus, this regulation provided by the SEBI acts as a provision for the Investor’s Protection”². The main objective of having this sort of collective investment scheme is to get some form of income or profit as a result of this investment.

Collective Investment Scheme: Under the Purview of SEBI

1. Securities Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulation, 1999

“SEBI regulations on the CIS specifically talk about the establishment of Collective Investment Management Company (CIMC) which means a corporation incorporated under the “Companies Act 2013”³ and also enrolled with the SEBI, whose purpose is to manage, deal, work, and arrange CIS. Only the Collective Investment Management Company which has obtained all the necessary

¹ Rajdeep Saini, “*Collective Investment Scheme: An Overview*”, Enterslice (Dec 03, 2020). <https://enterslice.com/learning/collective-investment-schemes-an-overview/>

² Deyasini Chakrabarti, “*All About Collective Investment Scheme*”, iPleaders (Mar 31, 2020). <https://blog.ipleaders.in/collective-investment-scheme-2/#Introduction>

³ The Companies Act, 2013, No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

certifications under the guidelines should only be allowed to support and continue the collective investment scheme.”⁴

2. Securities Exchange Board of India Act, 1992

“After the Securities Laws (Amendment) Act 31 of 1999, Section 11AA was inserted under the Securities Exchange Board of India Act 1992, which was effective from 22.02.2000. Section 11AA defines the Collective Investment Scheme. A CIS scheme or arrangement made or offered by any company under which the contributions, or payments made by the investors, by whatever name called, are pooled and utilized solely for the scheme or arrangement. The contributions or payments are made to such scheme or arrangement by the investors to receive profits, income, produce, or property, whether movable or immovable from such scheme or arrangement. The property, contribution, or investment forming part of the scheme or arrangement, whether identifiable or not, is managed on behalf of the investors. The investors do not have day-to-day control over the management and operation of the scheme or arrangement.”⁵

Collective Investment Scheme: History

In the earlier 1990s, some businessmen took plantation activities to a commercial level to support the Government’s efforts to prevent the destruction of forests in the country and also to channel private investments towards Agro plantation activities. The Government of

⁴ Securities Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Scheme) Regulations. 1999.

⁵ The Securities Exchange Board of India Act, 1992, Collective Investment Scheme, No. 15, Acts of Parliament, 1992 (India).

India observed these private investments and decided to regulate of such instruments (Agro Bonds & Plantation Bonds) and should be treated as a “Collective Investment Scheme” under the SEBI Act, 1992. On November 18, 1997, a press release was declared for the same. For the implementation of such a scheme, SEBI was asked to draft a regulation for investor protection and promotion of legitimate investment activity. “SEBI formulated a committee under the chairmanship of Dr. S.A. Dave along with the representatives from Regulatory Bodies, Plantation Industries & Consumer Forums.”⁶ Accordingly, Section 11AA was inserted under the SEBI Act 1992 for the concept of a Collective Investment Scheme. Such a Scheme was brought within the purview of securities to give statutory protection to the investors. “The phrase ‘units or any other instrument issued by any collective investment scheme to the investors in such schemes’ was inserted by the Securities Laws (Amendment) Act, 1999 within the definition of ‘securities’ in Section 2(h) of the Securities Contract (Regulation) Act, 1956.”⁷

The main objective of this scheme was to protect the investors most of whom are poor and uneducated or retired personnel or those who belong to a middle-income group and who seek to invest their hard-earned retirement benefits or savings in such schemes to earn some sustained benefits or with the fond hope that such investment will get appreciated in course of time. The Parliament thought it fit to introduce Section 11AA in the Act to ensure that any such scheme put to public notice is not intended to defraud such investors and also to monitor the operation of such schemes and arrangements based on the Regulations framed under section 11AA of the SEBI Act.⁸

⁶ Dave Committee, “*Report of the Committee on Collective Investment Schemes*”, Securities Exchange Board of India (Apr 05, 1999).

⁷ The Securities Contract (Regulation) Act, 1956, § 2(h)(ib), No. 42, Acts of Parliament, 1956 (India).

⁸ P.G.F. Limited vs. Union of India, AIR 2013 SC 3702, Para 37 and 38 (India).

Collective Investment Schemes: Characteristics

In India, CIS is a scheme or arrangement made or offered by any “person”⁹, under which:

- The contribution or payment made by the investors or other references of such investors, are pooled and utilized for such scheme or arrangement.
- The contribution or payments made under such scheme or arrangement by the investors to receive income, profits, productivity, or property, whether moveable or immovable, from such scheme or arrangement.
- The contribution, investment, or property forming part of such scheme or arrangement, whether identified or not, is managed on behalf of investors.
- The investors do not have overall control of the management and operation of such a scheme or arrangement.

Collective Investment Scheme: Exceptions

Following scheme or arrangement shall not be considered a Collective Investment Scheme:

1. *Co-operative Societies*

If any scheme, arrangement made or offered by a co-operative society registered under the “Co-operative Societies Act, 1912”¹⁰ or a society being a society registered or deemed to be registered under any law relating to co-operative societies for the time being in force in any State.

⁹ The Income Tax Act, 1961, § 2(31), No. 43, Acts of Parliament, 1961 (India).

¹⁰ The Co-operatives Societies Act, 1912, No. 2, Acts of Parliament, 1912 (India).

2. *Non-Banking Financial Companies (NBFC)*

If any scheme or arrangement made or offered under which deposits are accepted by non-banking financial companies is defined under “Section 45-I(f) of Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934”¹¹.

3. *Insurance*

If any scheme or arrangement was made or offered to be a contract of insurance under the “Insurance Act, 1938”¹².

4. *Provident Fund/Pension Fund*

If collection is made for any Scheme, Pension Scheme or Insurance Scheme framed under the “Employees Provident Fund and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952”¹³.

5. *Public Deposit*

If any collection is made under which deposits were accepted under “Section 73 of the Companies Act, 2013”¹⁴.

6. *Nidhi Company*

If any collection has been made under which deposits are accepted by a company declared as a Nidhi or a mutual benefit society under “Section 405 of the Companies Act, 2013”¹⁵.

¹¹ The Reserve Bank of India Act, 1934, NBFC, No. 2, Acts of Parliament, 1934 (India).

¹² The Insurance Act, 1938, No. 4, Acts of Parliament, 1938 (India).

¹³ The Employees Provident Funds and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952, No. 19, Acts of Parliament, 1952 (India).

¹⁴ The Companies Act, 2013, Prohibition on acceptance of deposits from public, No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

¹⁵ The Companies Act, 2013, Power of Central Government to direct companies to furnish information or statistics, No. 18, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

7. *Chit Fund*

If any collection is falling within the meaning of Chit business under the provision of “2(d) of Chit Fund Act, 1982”¹⁶.

8. *Mutual Fund*

If any collection is made under which contributions made are like a subscription to a mutual fund.

9. *Residuary Provision*

Any scheme or arrangement of the Central Government, in consultation with the SEBI notify.

Collective Investment Scheme: Registration of Collective Investment Management Company (CIMC)

CIMC is a company incorporated under the Companies Act 2013 & registered under SEBI to organize, operate & manage a CIS.¹⁷ Any person who proposes to carry on or sponsor or launch any scheme or arrangement which would be deemed to be a collective investment scheme under the CIMC on or after the commencement of SEBI (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999 shall make an application for the grant of registration to SEBI.¹⁸ CIMC shall not indulge in any other activities, except managing such scheme, acting as a trustee of any scheme, launching any scheme to invest in securities, and investing in any schemes floated by it. Although, CIMC may invest in its scheme if it makes a disclosure of its intention to invest in the offer document of the scheme, and does not charge any fees for its investment in that scheme.¹⁹ Only a

¹⁶ The Chit Funds Act, 1982, Chit Amount, No. 40, Acts of Parliament, 1982 (India).

¹⁷ Regulation 2(1) (h) of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

¹⁸ Regulation 4 & 4A of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

¹⁹ Regulation 13 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

CIMC that has obtained a certificate as per regulations shall carry on or sponsor or launch a collective investment scheme.²⁰

Collective Investment Scheme: Conditions for CIMC

“When the SEBI is satisfied with the application, SEBI calls upon the applicant to pay registration fees. On receipt of registration fees, SEBI shall grant the certificate only when certain terms and conditions are satisfied by the SEBI and must be in the interest of investors.”²¹

“Certain Conditions for registration of CIMC are:

1. The applicant must be registered as a company under the Companies Act, 2013.
2. The applicant must specify the managing of CIS as one of the main objectives under its Memorandum of Association (MoA).
3. The applicant must have a minimum net worth of rupees five crores. The exception to this is if the applicant does not have the minimum net worth, then at the time of making the application, the applicant must have a minimum of rupees three crores which shall be increased to rupees five crores within three years from the date of registration.
4. The applicant must follow the criteria specified in Schedule II of the “Securities and Exchange Board of India (Intermediaries) Regulations, 2008”²²
5. The applicant must follow the criteria specified in the Securities Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²⁰ Regulation 3 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²¹ Regulation 9 & 10 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²² Securities Exchange Board of India (Intermediaries) Regulations 2008.

6. The directors and key personnel of the applicant have not been convicted for an offense involving moral turpitude or for any economic offense or the violation of any securities laws.
7. At least 50% of the directors of CIMC must be independent. They shall not be directly or indirectly associated with the persons who have control over the Collective Investment Management Company.
8. No person, directly or indirectly connected with the applicant has in the past been refused registration by the SEBI. That person connected with the applicant has been rejected by the Board or any disciplinary action has been taken against such person under the rules and regulations made under the act.
9. At least one of the directors, on the Board of the CIMC who is not subject to retirement must be a representative of the trustee.
10. The CIMC must not be a trustee of any CIS.
11. The applicant must follow the criteria specified in the provisions of Chapter IX of the SEBI (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.”²³

Collective Investment Scheme: Terms & Conditions for Certificate

The certificate shall be granted after fulfilling the certain “terms & conditions”²⁴:

1. Any director of the CIMC must not be a director of another CIMC unless he’s an independent director

²³ Regulations 68 - 74 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²⁴ Regulation 11 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

and that person must be approved by the board of directors of other CIMC.

2. The CIMC must inform the board of directors about the change of information in the previously published information.
3. Appointment of a director of CIMC shall be made by the approval of the trustee.
4. CIMC shall comply with the provisions of SEBI (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.
5. There shall be no change in the controlling interest of CIMC without prior approval of SEBI, Trustee & Unit Holders.
6. CIMC must address the grievances of investors within one month from the date of receipt of the complaint.
7. CIMC shall agree with a depository for the dematerialization of the units of CIS proposed to be issued.
8. Subscription of units of CIS shall be paid back through cheque, demand draft, or other payment channels but not through cash.
9. The CIMC must comply with the KYC (Know your client) Norms specified by the SEBI.

*Terms & Conditions 7 – 9 were inserted after the 2014 Securities Law Amendment.²⁵

Collective Investment Scheme: The Trustee

1. A CIMC shall appoint a trustee who shall hold the

²⁵ Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) (Amendment) Regulations (Jan 09, 2014).

assets of the CIS for the benefit of unit holders.²⁶

2. Persons registered as a Debenture Trustee under the “SEBI (Debenture Trustee) Regulations, 1993”²⁷ are eligible for the position of trustee of such CIS but if that person directly or indirectly indulged with the control of CIMC is not eligible to be appointed as trustee.²⁸
3. As per the recommendations of the Dave Committee, it was stated that CIS shall be constituted in the form of a trust, and the instrument of the trust should be in the form of a deed registered under the “Indian Registration Act, 1908”²⁹ and shall be executed by CIMC in the favor of the trustee.³⁰
4. The Trustee and the CIMC shall agree on managing the scheme according to the SEBI Regulations to fulfill the scheme’s objectives.³¹
5. No scheme shall be launched by CIMC unless approved by the Trustee.³²

²⁶ Regulation 16(2) of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²⁷ Securities Exchange Board of India (Debenture Trustees) Regulations, 1993.

²⁸ Regulation 18(1) of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

²⁹ The Registrations Act, 1908, No. 16, Acts of Parliament, 1908 (India).

³⁰ Dave Committee, “*Report of the Committee on Collective Investment Schemes*”, Securities Exchange Board of India, Pg 14 (Apr 05, 1999). Regulation 16(1) of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

³¹ Regulation 20 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

³² Regulation 24 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

Collective Investment Scheme: Procedure for launching CIS

Every scheme shall be launched after following the due compliances:

1. CIMC must take the approval of the Trustee for launching the scheme.
2. CIMC must take ratings from a Rating Agency.
3. CIMC must take appraisals for the such scheme by an appraising agency.
4. CIMC must take an insurance policy for the protection of such schemes.
5. CIMC shall launch close-ended schemes whose duration shall not be less than of three calendar years.
6. CIMC must publish disclosure information stating that such schemes do not provide guaranteed returns.³³
7. The CIMC must issue Unit Certificate to its applicants within six weeks from the subscription list's closure date.
8. If the units are issued through depositories, then the "Securities Exchange Board of India (Depositories and Participants)"³⁴ Regulations must be followed.³⁵
9. The scheme units shall be listed with each and every stock exchange within six weeks from the scheme's closure.³⁶

³³ Regulation 24-25 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

³⁴ Securities Exchange Board of India (Depositories and Participants) Regulations, 1996.

³⁵ Regulation 32 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

³⁶ Regulation 36 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

Collective Investment Scheme: Action in case of default by CIS

1. Violation of SEBI Provisions and CIS Regulations.
2. Publishing of false or misleading information related to such regulations.
3. Does not cooperate with any inspection, investigation, or inquiry conducted by the SEBI under such provisions or regulations.
4. Fails to comply with the directions issued by the SEBI.
5. Fails to resolve the complaints of investors by the SEBI.
6. Breach of the Third Schedule provided under the Act.
7. Fails to pay the appropriate fees provided under the Second Schedule of the Act.
8. Fails to make an application for listing of units with the Stock Exchange.

Then the CIMC will be dealt with under the Chapter V of the “Securities and Exchange Board of India (Intermediaries) Regulations, 2008”^{37 38}.

Collective Investment Scheme: Penalties for default CIS

The Securities Exchange Board of India Act, 1992 has prescribed the provisions of penalties for default CIS³⁹:

- Sponsors who carry any CIS without obtaining a certificate of registration shall be liable for not less

³⁷ Securities Exchange Board of India (Intermediaries) Regulations, 2008.

³⁸ Regulation 59 of the Securities and Exchange Board of India (Collective Investment Schemes) Regulations, 1999.

³⁹ Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992, § 15D, No. 15, Acts of Parliament, 1992 (India).

than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.

- Fails to comply with the terms and conditions of the certificate of registration shall be liable for not less than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.
- Fails to make an application for listing such scheme shall be liable for not less than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.
- Fails to dispatch the unit certificates shall be liable for not less than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.
- Fails to return the application money to the investors shall be liable for not less than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.
- Fails to invest the money collected through CIS shall be liable for not less than one lakh rupees which may be extended to one lakh rupees for each day subjecting to a maximum of one crore rupees.

Collective Investment Scheme: Appeal

Any person who has been aggrieved by any order of the SEBI may appeal to the Securities Appellate Tribunal having jurisdiction in the matter.⁴⁰

⁴⁰ Securities and Exchange Board of India Act, 1992, § 15T, No. 15, Acts of Parliament, 1992 (India).

ROLE OF JUDICIARY IN PREVENTION OF CUSTODIAL DEATH WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO HUMAN RIGHT JURISPRUDENCE

Asma Ishaque*

Abstract

The incidents of custodial violence are not new for the Indian society. Human rights violation is the core of the criminal justice system and initiation of its action. This research article deals with the legal framework in India against torture and custodial violence and the role of the Indian police force in such crimes. It discusses the various rights to protection against torture and the role played by Indian judicial system to protect such human violation, besides giving guidelines through the verdicts of the supreme court of India. It refers to relevant laws of the country and the Constitution of India. The problem of custodial deaths frequently attracts the attention of press, NGO'S, in the field of human rights, political parties, people's representatives, National human rights commission, judiciary and all have contributed in their own way to trace the causes of custodial deaths and suggested remedies for its prevention.

Key Words: Custodial Violence, Torture, Criminal Justice System, Human Rights.

Introduction:

Justice to pretrial detainees is predominantly within the purview of the execution branch if government, particularly the police which often has negative approach in respect of individual's life liberty

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and human dignity a concept basis to the norms of justice. Use of third degree methods by the police , atrocities, harassment , cruelty to men and women detained in custody, molestation , rapes, physical and mental torture, exploitation, coercing near relatives of the alleged accused for early surrender, not registering genuine complaints , custodial death etc are common grievances of the pre-trial detainees. Under such precarious conditions justice to pre-trial detainees is a pertinent question of human rights, constitutional guarantees, protection of detainees under substantive laws and special statutes, invite special concern and assume great significance. Ambit of Human Rights represent such natural rights which lead and contribute to a balanced development of individual guaranteeing life, liberty and dignity of human beings, protecting from oppressions, mal-practices cruelty, slavery, servitude, arbitrary arrests, inhuman or degrading treatment of the individuals by the executive and ensuring equality before law.

Constitution of India also guarantees that no person shall be deprived of this life or personal liberty except according to procedure established by Law. Encroachment upon personal liberty by executive is not permitted save in accordance with law, and in conformity with the provisions thereof. There is not doctrine of state necessity in India. Before a person is deprived of his life or personal liberty the procedure established by law must be strictly followed and must not be advantage of the person affected.

Prior to *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*¹ Article 21 was construed narrowly only as a guarantee against executive action unsupported by law. But *Maneka's* case opened up a new dimension and laid down that it imposed a limitation upon law-making as well, namely, that while prescribing a procedure for depriving a person of his life or personal liberty, it must prescribe a procedure which is reasonable, fair and just. Court on receiving

¹ AIR 1978 SC597

complaint of deprivation- of such a right, under its power of judicial review, has to decide whether there is a law authorizing such deprivation and whether, in the given case, the procedure prescribed by such law is reasonable, fair and just and not arbitrary, whimsical and fanciful.

Apart from Human Rights and Constitutional guarantees, substantive Law, such as Indian Penal Code, Criminal Procedure Code, Evidence Act and special Statutes also provide protection against atrocities and exploitation of Individuals. Section 330 of the Indian Penal Code lays down that whoever voluntarily causes hurt for the purpose of extorting from the sufferer or any person interested in him any confession or any information which may lead to the detection of an offence or restoration of any 2 property or valuable security, shall be punished with imprisonment for a term which may extend to seven years and shall also be liable to fine. In spite of legal guarantees and protection, violation of fundamental rights of citizens by the custodians of law and order is the rule rather than exception. The law becomes a mockery when its enforcement agencies begin to indulge in lawlessness. Crime figures in such conditions are bound to go up if the machinery meant for its prevention and control happens to have a culpable conduct.

Torture including rape and ill-treatment were endemic throughout the country. Victims included suspected political activists, Criminal suspects, members of vulnerable groups, and those defending economic and social rights. In February, seven men who had been detained by police for several days were admitted to hospital in Rajkot, Gujrat state, with serious eye injuries. Police officials had apparently rubbed a medicinal balm and chilli powder into their eyes. According to reports, the detainees had been ordered to strip and slap one another before being thrashed with belts. Investigations into the incident were continuing at the end of year. There were increasing reports of rape by members of the armed forces. In September, an 18 years old girl was allegedly raped by

soldiers during a search operation in her village in Assam. Doctor confirmed that she had been raped. No action was known to have been taken against the alleged perpetrators

Law is to protect liberties. But the state authorities and its duty to maintain law and order at any cost are always in conflict with the human feelings and the liberty of the people. Liberty as history has shown is the basic thing that goes to make up the ethos of man and civilization without it no one can attain happiness. Which is the ultimate objective of the human being but liberty has to be regulated so that all may enjoy it equally. Absolute liberty is neither possible nor exist in any society whatsoever.

Safeguards Available to Pre-trial Detainees

The human being is the beginning and the end of all organized societies within the state or within the international community. In the present set of society, the state has the fundamental task to create conditions of life affording adequate protection to the individual person. The realization of human rights must be effected in every country within the pattern of national life. The International Law of human rights must be interpreted, applied and enforced in every country with proper care which builds up the collective character of the peoples.

National safeguards are to be studied under the head of Protection of Human Rights Act, constitutional guarantee and protection under substantive law of the land.

- i. “Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993” India being a signatory to the U.N Charter, The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and, number of conventions related thereto, decided to pass an. Act to provide, promote Human Rights, and make their implementation more effective, safe and protective. Thus the Act of 1993, was passed and made effective on 8th january,1994 with an aim to constitute a National Human Rights Commission, State Human Rights

Commissions in State and Human Rights Courts for hearing grievances of Human Rights oppressions and redress them effectively.

- ii. Constitutional Guarantees and Protection under ordinary Laws of Land. It is well known that if the pre-trial events manage mainly by the police are not subject to the control of the constitution they may render administration of justice almost impossible. Example may be given of 1975 during emergency the deflation of fundamental rights reached the high water mark. The disturbing disclosure of emergency excesses before the Shah Commission brought the police system and the criminal justice system into disrepute. With the lifting of emergency the judiciary again re-discovered its role, democratic liberalism resurgence and regained the legitimacy forfeited partially. Therefore, for criminal administration of justice constitutional control is the basic requirement.
- iii. Right against Self Incrimination: The Suspect/ accused in India have a right to refuse to answer any incriminating questions and as pronounced by the apex court in *Nandini Satpati*² has a right to silence in custodial interrogation. The court held that any mode of pressure by the police whether subtle or crude, mental or physical, direct or indirect is violative of the rights against self incrimination. The constitutional right against self incrimination under Article 20 (3) is reiterated in Sections 24, 25, 26 and 27 of the Indian Evidence Act which excludes involuntary confessions by conclusively presuming all confessions to police and in police custody as involuntary.
- iv. Torture Commission of 1858 report was the reason for these provisions in the Indian Evidence Act, which are intended to discourage police from torturing the suspects /accused in

² A.I.R 1978 SCR(3) 608

their custody. Similarly, Sections 162, 163 (1), 315, and 342 (a) of the Code of Criminal Procedure are designed towards prohibiting torture of suspects /accused by the police. Right to be informed of the ground of arrest, right to consult a legal practitioner, right to be produced before a judicial magistrate within 24 hours of police custody, etc., are the other rights assured by Article 22 of the Constitution and sections 57, 167 of the Code of Criminal Procedure.

- v. Critical evaluation of the role of National Human Rights Commission shows that the Commission acted very effectively in investigating into all custodial deaths and the commissions guidelines issued from time to time has salutary effect. But the study reveals that the commission's directions with regard to payment to compensation were followed by the States but its directions to prosecute the erring police personnel were not heeded.
1. The Government should acknowledge the reality of widespread torture practices and against a commission (like the Torture Commission of British days or more appropriately, like the truth and Reconciliation commission of South Africa which enquired into all torture practices) to conduct a full fledged enquiry into the torture practices indulged in by the police against ordinary suspects as well as political activists and suspected terrorists.
 2. The Government should at the earliest ratify the Convention against torture and carry out the obligations under the Convention, such as enacting a special law against torture (like the Torture Victims Protection Act of USA). Such a law should consolidate and incorporate all the guidelines issued by the Supreme Court and NHRC on custodial deaths from time to time. In specific, such a law should provide for:

- a. Impartial and speedy enquiry into all allegations of custodial torture and deaths by judicial officers and ensure quick prosecution of the guilty police personnel,
- b. Presumption of guilt against the Station House Officer (or other responsible official for detention as the case may be) for torture and death and the burden of proof shall be placed on the concerned official to prove his innocence, as suggested by the 113th Report of the Law Commission,
- c. Plugging the loopholes and strengthening the existing safeguards regarding arrest, period of police custody etc that are provided in the Constitution and various laws,
- d. Constitution of independent bodies at the district level consisting of persons of integrity and human rights understanding, who shall have unlimited access to any place where persons are deprived of their liberty, including the right to move inside such places without restriction, the power to interview in private persons deprived of their liberty, the power to see all buildings and installations - not only the cells, the power to sell all papers - not only the records of those detained, the power to make surprise visits at any time,
- e. Continuous education of people on human rights, in particular the detainees of their rights,
- f. Medical treatment of victims of torture,
- g. Statutory right for compensation.

Joint Committee on Human Rights under authority of House of Lords and House of Commons (2004) in U.K. shows that 38 deaths in Police custody have been reported in England and Wales between April 2003 to March 2004. There were 7 deaths in police stations, 22 in hospitals, and the remaining were reported for the scene of arrest or following arrest. None of the deaths at police station involved the use of restraint, although six of those who died in hospitals had been restrained by the police shortly prior to death. All of those who died at police stations were white; one of those who died in hospital having earlier been restrained was black. In 2002-03, there were 8 deaths in police custody in Scotland. In 2001, there were 5 deaths in police custody in Northern Ireland. A research study by the POLICE COMPLAINTS AUTHORITY (PCA) illustrates the extreme vulnerability of those who die in police custody. The PCA found that, in the period between 1998-2003, there was an over 10 representation of ethnic minorities in deaths in police custody. The study also found that there were restraint issues in a higher proportion of the deaths involving nonwhite individuals than among white individuals. There are very high rates of drug and alcohol dependency, and of mental illness, amongst those who died in police custody. The PCA survey found that just half of those who died had prior indications of mental health problem. The study concluded that the vulnerable people are dying in the custody of state and no coordination between police custody and mental health Act which may prevent the malady.

Similarly, Human Rights watch (1998) an international

organization working for human rights conducted a study on SHIELDED FROM JUSTICE: POLICE BRUTALITY IN THE UNITED STATES in U.S.A. The study found the followings are contributing factors in police custody.

- (i) Weak Civilian Review Citizen review agencies, tasked with monitoring and, in some cases, investigating cases of excessive force, are under funded by city officers who refuse to cooperate with them, under attack by police unions and others, and underutilized by the public. External citizen review should be an integral part of police oversight and policy formulation, but instead has been sidelined in most cities examined.
- (ii) Leadership Failure Police administrators, the officials most responsible for addressing the problem of police abuse, are not yet taking issue seriously. Lack of effective leadership and the failure of the judiciary system are the major shortcoming common to all the cities. The study concludes that the problem of excessive use of force is “fundamentally” a problem of supervision, management and leadership.
- (iii) Ineffective Civil Remedies In past because police often are not held responsible for their actions through administrative or criminal proceedings, many police abuse victims or their families rely solely on civil remedies for redress. In practice, civil lawsuits usually allow police departments to continue to ignore abuses committed by officer. Some victims have succeeded in obtaining compensation, and a small percentage of civil lawsuits have forced police department to accept liability for abuses, leading to reforms in training or flawed policies.

- (iv) Race as a factor Race continues to play a central role in the use of excessive force in the United States. In 1991, Christopher Commission was set up to examine the Rodney King beating case.

Custodial crime in Indian

The review of empirical studies on custodial crimes in Indian context includes various studies undertaken by individuals, academic institutions, police research and training institutions, non government organizations and various Committees and Commissions. These studies have been broadly divided into five sub-themes such as

- (a) Illegal arrest and detention;
- (b) Custodial violence;
- (c) Custodial torture & deaths;
- (d) Custodial rapes and other abuses against women and
- (e) Disappearances

Illegal Arrest and Detention

Although it is prohibited under Constitution and legal provisions and International law, the illegal detention is a common phenomenon in every part of India. Few studies that have been conducted have focused on the issue. Over the years, it is significant that arrests made by police under the Local and Special Laws are around twice as compare to the arrest under the Indian Penal Code. It is noteworthy to mention here that arrests under Indian Penal Code, 1860 are usually based on individual complaints which might provide some immediate and direct reasons for police to make arrest offenders to satisfy the aggrieved person against whom crime committed.

However, on the other hand, majority of the arrests under the local and special laws related to prohibited laws such as Excise Act,

Arms Act, Gambling Act, Suppression of Immoral Traffic Act, Motor vehicle Act etc. In such cases, no complaint registered by aggrieved parties as such but merely on information and intelligence available to the police in their field work arrests are made. Thus a large number of persons arrested every year would view the police as having acted harshly on their own information network and not by complainants. A large section of the arrest of this types belong to preventive part of police functioning on the basis of their discretionary decision which not only affect police image among the public but also provide as scope for malpractice and highhandedness.

As National Police Commission (1981) estimates that around 60% of total arrests made by police are unnecessary and unjustified. This discriminatory practice is very common in India. Moreover, the incident of informal arrest is more common in the police stations located in rural areas where awareness about their rights against unlawful arrest is minimal. It was also found a kind of police sub-culture prevailing in the police organization (Bajpai, 2000). But, illegal arrest and detention reported to continuing even after the ruling of the Supreme Court in leading cases of *Joginder Kumar v. State of Uttar Pradesh*³ and *D.K. Basu v. State of West Bengal*⁴

Landmark Judgments on Custodial Death:

In all of its recent decision of the Supreme Court one finds extensive reference of the human rights by the Supreme Court of India, particularly for protecting prisoners from various inhuman and barbarous treatments. Custodial crime which includes deaths in police custody has drowned attention of public media and legislature over the past many years. Despite human rights laws and constitutional jurisprudence, the police are still using third degree

³ AIR 1994 4 SCC 260 Cr. L.J.

⁴ AIR1997SC 610.

methods and illegal torture which often lead to custodial deaths. This represents a grim drawback of the legal system.

Joginder Kumar v. State Of U.P and Others⁵

The rights are inherent in Articles 21 and 22(1) of the Constitution and require be recognising and scrupulously protecting. For effective enforcement of these fundamental rights, Hon'ble Court issued the following guidelines:

The police officer shall inform the arrested person when he is brought to the police station of this right. An entry shall be required to be made in the diary as to who was informed of the arrest. These protections from power must be held to flow from Articles 21 and 22 (1) and enforced strictly. It was further directed that, it shall be the duty of the Magistrate, before whom the arrested person is produced, to satisfy himself that these requirements have been complied with.

J. Prabhavathiamma v/s The State of Kerala & Others⁶

The two serving police personnel were awarded the death sentence by a CBI court, after hearing the case for over a decade, in Thiruvananthapuram, over the death of a scrap metal shop worker, who the court believes was murdered in custody.

While sentencing the two, Judge J Nazar had said: "This is a brutal and dastardly murder by accused (number) one and two... The acts of the accused persons would definitely adversely affect the very institution of the police department... If the faith of the people in the institution is lost, that will affect the public order and law and order, and it is a dangerous situation.

D.K. Basu v. State of West Bengal.

The Court issued a list of 11 guidelines in addition to the

⁵ *AIR 1349: 1994 SCC (4) 260*

⁶ WP(C) NO 24258 OF 2007(K) and CRL .R.P.2902 OF 2007

Constitutional and Statutory Safeguards to be followed in all cases of arrest and detention. The guidelines are as follows: –Details of all personnel handling the interrogations of the arrested person must be recorded in a register. A memorandum of arrest at the time of the arrest should be prepared. It must also be signed by the detainee and must contain the time and date of the arrest. Police must notify a detainee’s time, place of detention, and place of custody. Police of the affected area telegraphically within the period of 8 to 12 hours after the arrest. An entry must be made in the Case Diary at the place of detention. The “Inspection Memo” must be signed by both the detainee and the arresting police officer and a copy must be provided to the detainee. The detainee must undergo a medical examination by a trained physician every 48 hours while in custodial. Copies of all documents, including the arrest memo, must be sent to the Magistrate for registration.

In recently, Jayaraj Bennex Custodial case on 19 June 2020 Jayaraj and his son Bennex were picked up for inquiry by the Tamil Nadu police in Sathankulam, Thoothukudi district after a heated argument over closure of their during the lockdown. They were taken to the police station and booked on charges of disobedience to order duly promulgated by public servant, preventing a public servant from discharging duties by using criminal force and also negligent act that was likely to spread infection of disease dangerous to life. They were produce in magistered court and remanded in judicial custody. The police took them to the sub-jail where the visible bodily injuries were entered in the registered. Jayaraj and his So Bennex reported health issues after which prison official first called in a doctor and then shifted them to the government hospital where they died. The incident sparked instant protests from traders, human rights activists and political parties who accused the police of high handedness and demanded that a case be registered against those responsible for the excesses. The Madurai bench of the Madras High Court that took suo moto cognizance of the incident has ordered a court monitored

investigation into the case.⁷

Conclusion

Death in police custody is one of the worst kinds of crime in a civilized society. Custodial death in police stations even in jail seems to be common happening these days. There are numerous laws available in the country but enforcing agencies are making no appropriate use of them.

Laws are rules written on paper that can be overlooked very easily by any person if not sensitized and motivated. In most cases, the poor couldn't fight against them due to police threat and the financial situation, being walls between them and justice. However, the custodial deaths are becoming an issue, yet people's opinions towards the police are quite negative. The NHRC will intervene of course when it comes to the violation of human rights in prisons. But if an organization like the UN fails to stop wars, how could NHRC prevent the police from committing atrocities. Force is indeed a necessary evil to prevent any future crime in society. It is up to judiciary to take action against custodial deaths as they have the power over the police. It is high time that the laws become stricter just to protect the victims and punish the perpetrators of the custodial deaths.

⁷ The Hindu newspaper, June 28, 2020

ENFORCEABILITY OF NON-COMPETE COVENANTS IN EMPLOYMENT CONTRACTS VIS-À-VIS JUDICIAL PRONOUNCEMENTS IN INDIA

Shantanu Haldavnekar*

Abstract

In order to protect commercial interests employers often resort to Non-Compete covenants while entering into employment contracts with their employees. The present Article deals with the enforceability of such Non-Compete covenants vis-a-vis Judicial Pronouncements in India. At the outset, the present Article talks about Statutory Provision that governs the Non-Compete covenants in India and object behind such a provision. The Article then sheds light upon enforceability of and distinction between Non-Compete clauses that operate during the term of employment and Non-Compete clauses that operate after the termination of the term of employment. Article then proceeds to deal with the effect of premature termination of employment. Besides, it also deals with the aspect of reasonable and partial nature of restraints imposed by Non-Compete covenants and the validity of the same. Further the present Article analyses the view taken by Courts with regard to disparity of bargaining power between an employee and an employer while entering into employment contracts. Article also deals with the aspect of recovery of damages when an employer expends money on training of the employee and the employee in return leaves the job prior to the termination of employment period as stipulated in the employment contract. Further, the Article examines, whether covenants that prohibit employees from divulging trade secrets of the employer and soliciting customers or employees of the erstwhile employers operate after the termination

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of employment period or not ? Lastly, the Article sheds light upon meaning and enforceability of Garden Leave clauses.

Introduction

Non-Compete clause in an employment agreement provides that an employee must not enter into competition with the employer. It usually contains negative covenants preventing the employee from engaging himself in a similar business during and/or after the period of employment. The law relating to legality of Non-Compete agreements is no more *Res Integra* and has been dealt by Indian Courts extensively.

Statutory Provision and its Object

Section 27 of the Indian Contract Act, 1872 proclaims that agreement by which one is restrained from exercising lawful profession, trade or business, of any kind is void to that extent. Section 27 also carves out an exception to this general rule by providing for discretionary power of parties to enter into an agreement by which the seller of the good will of business may agree with buyer to refrain from carrying on a similar business, within specified local limits, so long as the buyer, or any person deriving title to the good-will from him, carries on a like business therein, provided that such limits appear to the Court reasonable, regard being had to the nature of the business.¹

Freedom to practise any profession, or to carry on any occupation, trade or business is a Fundamental Right protected by the Constitution of India. Just as the Legislature cannot take away individual freedom of trade, so also the Individual cannot barter it away by agreement.² Public policy requires that every man shall be at liberty to work for himself, and shall not be at liberty to deprive

¹ Indian Contract Act, 1872, § 27, No. 9, Acts of Parliament, 1872 (India).

² Avatar Singh, Contract and Specific Relief, 291 (Eastern Book Company, 2017).

himself or the State of his labour, skill or talent, by any contract that he enters into.³ Every man should have unfettered liberty to exercise his powers and capacities for his own and the Community's benefit.⁴

While guarding zealously the freedom of contract to engage in any trade, business or profession as one wills, the law abhors monopoly which prohibits a person from pursuing a lawful trade, business or profession.⁵

Restraints during the Term of Employment per Contra Restraints after Termination of the Term of Employment

There is a clear distinction between a restriction in a contract of employment which is operative during the period of employment and one which is to operate after the termination of employment.⁶ Negative covenants operative during the period of employment when the employee is bound to serve his employer exclusively are not to be regarded as restraint of trade and therefore do not fall under Section 27 of the Contract Act.⁷ Such agreements are enforceable, the reason being that the doctrine of restraint of trade never applies during the continuance of a contract of employment and applies only when the contract comes to an end.⁸ When a contract only ties the parties during the continuance of the contract, and the negative ties are only those which are incidental and normal to the positive commercial arrangements at which the contract

³ *Leather Cloth Co v. Lorson*, (1869) LR 9 EQ 345

⁴ *Vancouver Malt & Sake Brewing Co. Ltd v. Vancouver Breweries Ltd*, AIR 1934 PC 101.

⁵ *Taprogge GesellschaftMbh v. Iaec India Ltd.*, AIR 1988 Bom 157.

⁶ *Superintendence Company of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*, 1980 AIR 1717.

⁷ *Niranjan Shankar Golikari v. Century Spinning and Mfg. Co. Ltd.*, 1967 AIR 1098.

⁸ *Superintendence Company Of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*, 1980 AIR 1717.

aims, even though those ties exclude all dealings with others, there is no restraint of trade. If, however, the contract ties the trading activities of either party after its determination, it is a restraint of trade.⁹

The Honourable Apex Court affirmed the law laid down in aforesaid judgments in *Gujarat Bottling Co. Ltd. and Ors. v. Coca Cola Company and Ors.*¹⁰

The purpose which a restraint is expected to serve determines the character of the restraint. For instance the restraints which operate during the term of the contract have to fulfil one kind of purpose viz. furthering the contract. On the other hand, the restraints operative after the termination of the contract strive to secure freedom from competition from a person who no longer works within the contract. The negative covenants operative during the term of the contract are not hit by Section 27 of the Contract Act because they are designed to fulfil the contract and not to restrict them. On the other hand, when a restriction applies after the contract is terminated, the restriction on freedom of trade, business or profession takes the form of restraint on trade, business or profession.¹¹

Negative covenants tied up with positive covenants during the subsistence of a contract be it of employment, partnership, commerce, agency or the like, would not normally be regarded as being in restraint of trade, business or profession unless the same are unconscionable or wholly one-sided. No employee can be confronted with the situation where he has to either work for the present employer or be forced to idleness¹²

⁹ *Esso Petroleum Co. Ltd. v. Harper's Garage (Stourport) Ltd.*, (1968) AC 269.

¹⁰ MANU/SC/0472/1995.

¹¹ *Taprogge GesellschaftMbh v. Iaec India Ltd.*, AIR 1988 Bom 157.

¹² *Wipro Ltd. v. Beckman Coulter International SA*, 2006 (3) ARBLR 118 (Delhi).

In other words, the doctrine of restraint of trade never applies during continuance of the contract of employment it applies only when the contract comes to an end. The Courts, therefore, view with disfavour a restrictive covenant by an employee not to engage in a business similar to or competitive with that of the employer after termination of the contract of his employment.¹³

Partial or Limited Restraint

A Contract which has for its object a restraint of trade is, prima facie void. The question whether an agreement is void under section 27 of the Contract Act must be decided upon the wording of that section. There is nothing in the wording of section 27 to suggest that the principle stated therein does not apply when the restraint is for a limited period only or is confined to a particular area. Such matters of partial restriction have effect only when the fact falls within the exception carved out in Section 27. Section 27 of the Contract Act is general in terms, and declares all agreements in restraint of trade, etc. void pro tanto, except in the case specified in the exception and unless a particular Contract can be distinctly brought within that exception there is no escape from the prohibition.¹⁴ As held by the Supreme Court in *Percept D'Mark (India) Pvt. Ltd. v. Zaheer Khan*,¹⁵ neither the test of reasonableness nor the principle of the restraint being partial would be applicable unless it falls in the exception carved out in Section 27.

The words 'restraint from exercising a lawful profession, trade or business' do not mean an absolute restriction, and are intended to apply to a partial restriction as well, a restriction limited to some particular place, otherwise the first exception would have been

¹³ In *IEC School of Art & Fashion v. Mr Gursharan Goyal and Ors.*, 72 (1998) DLT 833.

¹⁴ *Superintendence Company of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*, 1980 AIR 1717.

¹⁵ (2006) 4 SCC 227.

unnecessary. Moreover, ‘in the following Section (i.e. Section 28) the legislative authority when it intends to speak of an absolute restraint and not a partial one, has introduced the word ‘absolutely’. The use of this word in Section 28 supports the view that in Section 27 it was intended to prevent not merely a total restraint from carrying on trade or business, but a partial one as well. The Courts have nothing to do with the policy of such a law. All they have to do is to take the words of the Contract Act, and put upon them the meaning which they appear plainly to bear.¹⁶ It was held by the Supreme Court that the aforesaid test laid down, had stood the test of time and had invariably been followed by all the High Courts in India.¹⁷ The question of reasonableness as also the question of whether the restraint is partial or complete is not required to be considered at all whenever an issue arises as to whether a particular term of a contract is or is not in restraint of trade, business or profession.¹⁸

The Supreme Court in *Gujarat Bottling Co. Ltd. and Ors. v. Coca Cola Company and Ors.*,¹⁹ observed that it will proceed on the basis that an enquiry into reasonableness of the restraint is not envisaged by Section 27 of the Contract Act.

The Law Commission in its Thirteenth Report has recommended that the provision in Section 27 of Contract Act should be suitably amended to allow reasonable restrictions and all contracts in restraint of trade, general or partial, as were reasonable, However, the Parliament by keeping the interest of the parties as well as of the public has not taken any action on the said recommendation.

¹⁶ *MadhubChunder v. Raj Coomar Doss*: 14 BLR 76 (1874).

¹⁷ *Superintendence Company of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*, 1980 AIR 1717.

¹⁸ *Wipro Ltd. v. Beckman Coulter International SA*, 2006 (3) ARBLR 118 (Delhi).

¹⁹ MANU/SC/0472/1995.

Disparity of Bargaining Power

It is well established that employee's covenant should be carefully scrutinised because there is inequality of bargaining power between the parties indeed no bargaining power may occur because the employee is presented with a standard form of contract to accept or reject. At the time of the agreement, the employee may have given little thought to the restriction because of his eagerness for a job; such contracts tempt improvident persons, for the sake of present gain, to deprive themselves of the power to make future acquisitions and expose them to imposition and oppression.²⁰

While construing a restrictive or negative covenant and for determining whether such covenant is in restraint of trade, business or profession or not, the courts take a stricter view in employer-employee contracts than in other contracts, such as partnership contracts, collaboration contracts, franchise contracts, agency/distributorship contracts, commercial contracts. The reason being that in the latter kind of contracts, the parties are expected to have dealt with each other on more or less an equal footing, whereas in employer-employee contracts, the norm is that the employer has an advantage over the employee and it is quite often the case that employees have to sign standard form contracts or not be employed at all.²¹

Effect of Premature Removal

In *Superintendence Company of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*,²² the appellant company terminated the respondent's services in contrast to respondent voluntarily leaving the service. The Supreme Court while interpreting the term 'leave' in the Non-

²⁰ *Superintendence Company of India (P) Ltd. v. Krishan Murgai*, 1980 AIR 1717.

²¹ *Wipro Ltd. v. Beckman Coulter International SA*, 2006 (3) ARBLR 118 (Delhi).

²² 1980 AIR 1717.

Compete Clause observed that The word ‘leave’ has various shades of meaning depending upon the context of intent with which it is used. According to the plain meaning, the word ‘leave’ in relation to an employee, should be construed to mean where he ‘voluntarily’ leaves i.e. of his own volition and does not include a case of dismissal. The word ‘leave’ appears to connote voluntary action, and is synonymous with the word ‘quit’. It does not refer to the expulsion of an employee by the act of his employer without his consent and against his remonstrance. The Court further held that a restraint beyond the term of service is prima facie void but even if it is assumed to be valid, it will only apply after the expiry of the term in its natural course, and not when the employee is wrongfully dismissed earlier.

When the term of employment was not for a specified period and employee left the job, no restraint was allowed to be imposed upon such an employee.²³

Recovery of Training Expenses

In *Nazir Maricar v. Marshalls Sons & Co. India Ltd*²⁴, The agreement mandated that the employee would put in service for a period of five years after returning from training abroad at the cost of the employer. The employee left after 18 months. The Trial Court awarded the employer whole of the damages as quantified in indemnity clause. However, the High Court reduced the amount keeping in mind the proportionate recovery already effected during the period of service. The Court held that there is no restraint in such agreements since the employee is free to go away after paying unrecovered portion of expenses of training. The Court also noted that such agreements are for the benefit of employees because training provided to them increases their acceptability in the job market.

²³ *Weiler International Electronics (P) Ltd. v. PunitaVelu Somasundaram*, (2003) 3 BOM CR 59.

²⁴ (2005) 2 CTC 478.

When the employee abruptly left the Company the High Court held that such action by the employee did not cause any damage or loss to the company and it would be unreasonable to acquire from the employee the amount as per the terms of employment bond, viz. liquidated damages of Rs. 2,00,000 along with stipend charges and additional expenses incurred by the company for the defendant. An amount of Rs. 100, 000 was fixed by the court as reasonable damages taking into consideration the period of work and the fact that no actual loss was caused to the Company²⁵.

The employer is required to establish that the employee was the beneficiary of special favour or concession or training at the cost and expense wholly or in part of the employer and there had been a breach of the undertaking by the beneficiary of the same. In such cases, the breach would per se constitute the required legal injury resulting to the employer due to breach of the contract. The employer was entitled to recover the stipulated damages, which is a genuine pre- estimate by the parties of the damages incurred. There is no requirement to prove separately any post-breach damages.²⁶

When there was no occasion for the employee to undergo training or the employer to incur any expenses on training, and there were no training expenses incurred on the employee by the employer, the Delhi High Court observed that expenses incurred by the employer towards carrying out the process of appointment including advertisement, or the expenses incurred in future for making an appointment against the vacancy arisen because of the employee's resignation cannot be treated as amounts reimbursable by the employee.²⁷

²⁵ Satyam Computer Services Limited v. LadellaRavichander, MANU/AP/0416/2011.

²⁶ Toshnial Brothers (Pvt.) Ltd. v. E.Eswarprasad&Ors., 1997 LLR 500.

²⁷ Kailash Kumar v. Syndicate Bank Ltd.,2018 IAD (Delhi) 444.

Non Solicitation and Poaching

Non Solicitation clause forbids former employees from soliciting former employer's Customers, Clients, etc. It also forbids poaching by former employees of current employees of the former employer. Such clauses are usually drafted to remain operative during the term of employment and for some reasonable time period after the termination of employment.

The Delhi High Court in *Eli Research India Pvt. Ltd. v. Deepak Gupta and Ors*²⁸, held that defendant (former employee) would not poach any employee of the plaintiff nor induce any third party or individual to cease or modify its relationship with the plaintiff even after the termination of the employment with the plaintiff. However, the Court, as per the settled position of law, held the negative covenant which restricted the former employee from engaging in competing business post termination of the employment period as void.

In *Desiccant Rotors International Pvt. Ltd. v. Bappaditya Sarkar &Anr.*,²⁹ the Delhi High Court allowed an injunction against the manager prohibiting him from soliciting Desiccant's customers and suppliers. However, merely approaching customers of a previous employer does not amount to solicitation until orders have been placed by such customers based on such approach.³⁰ Non Solicitation clauses may be valid if reasonable restrictions such as distance, reasonable time frame, protection and non-usage of trade secrets and goodwill are imposed on former employees.³¹

Acts of soliciting committed by former employees take such active

²⁸ MANU/DE/1388/2017.

²⁹ Delhi HC, CS (OS) No. 337/2008 (decided on July 14, 2009).

³⁰ *M/s.FLSmidthPvt.Ltd. v M/s.SecanInvescast (India) Pvt.Ltd.*, (2013) 1 CTC 886.

³¹ *M/s.FLSmidthPvt.Ltd. v M/s.SecanInvescast (India) Pvt.Ltd.*, (2013) 1 CTC 886.

form that it induces the customers of the former employer to break their contract with the former employer and enter into a contract with the former employee, or prevent other persons from entering into contracts with the former employer cannot be permitted.³²

The Delhi High Court in *Wipro Limited vs Beckman Coulter International S.A.*³³, held that the non-solicitation clause does not amount to a restraint of trade, business or profession and would not be hit by Section 27 of the Indian Contract Act, 1872 as being void. However, it should be noted that in the present case the Contract was not a contract between an employer and an employee. The parties were restrained for a period of two years from the date of termination of the agreement, from soliciting, inducing or encouraging any employees of the other party to terminate his employment with or to accept employment with any competitor, supplier or customer of the other party. It was a covenant which essentially prohibited either party from enticing and/or alluring each other's employees away from their respective employments. It was a restriction casted upon the contracting parties and not on the employees. The Court observed that "in the present Contract there is no bar on the employees of the petitioner leaving its employment and joining the respondent and vice versa. The bar or restriction is on the petitioner and the respondent from offering inducements to the other's employees to give up employment and join them. Therefore, the clause by itself does not put any restriction on the employees. The restriction is put on the petitioner and the respondent and, therefore, has to be viewed more liberally than a restriction in an employer-employee contract."

Safeguarding Trade Secrets

In Hi Tech Systems and Services Ltd. v. Suprabhat Ray,³⁴ when

³² *Embee Software Pvt. Ltd. v. Samir Kumar Shaw*, AIR 2012 Cal 141.

³³ 2006 (3) ARBLR 118 Delhi.

³⁴ AIR 2015 Cal 261.

respondents acted in breach of Contract terms and they were in process of utilizing trade secrets and confidential information, the Supreme Court restrained the respondents from acting as sales agent of other companies.

When former employees were carrying out similar business they were restrained by the Delhi High Court from using substantial imitation or reproduction of the industrial drawings of the plaintiffs or from using in any other manner whatsoever the technical knowhow, specifications or drawings of the plaintiffs.³⁵

In *Mr. Diljeet Titus, Advocate v. Mr. Alfred A. Adebare and Ors*,³⁶ the Delhi High Court restrained defendants from using the copied material of the plaintiff post the termination of employment with plaintiff but allowed them to carry on their profession, utilize the skills and information they have mentally retained. The Court enjoined that the defendants having worked with the plaintiff cannot utilize the agreements, due diligence reports, list of clients and all such material which has come to their knowledge or has been developed during their relationship with the plaintiff and which is per se confidential. It is obvious that the 'doctrine of restraint' on trade secrets can be invoked even after the service or employment period has come to an end. Indeed, a 'restrictive covenant' can operate only during the employment period. But, that does not mean that restrictions cannot be imposed so as to ensure that doctrine of restraint regarding the trade secrets after the employment or service period has come to an end.³⁷ A clause prohibiting an employee from disclosing commercial or trade secrets is not in restraint of trade because the employee is not

³⁵ *Escorts Const. Equipment Ltd v. Action Const. Equipment P. Ltd.*, AIR 1999 Delhi 73.

³⁶ 130 (2006) DLT 330.

³⁷ *Kuoni Travel (India) Private Limited v. Ashish Kishore*, 2007(6) ALL MR 808.

thereby restrained from carrying on any lawful profession, trade or business.³⁸

However, anyone in employment for some period would know certain facts and would come to know certain information without any special efforts and the same cannot be said to amount to trade secrets or confidential information.³⁹

A trade secret is some protected and confidential information which the employee has acquired in the course of his employment and which should not reach others in the interest of the employer. A trade secret can be a formulae, technical know-how or a peculiar mode or method of business adopted by an employer which is unknown to others. However, routine day-to-day affairs of employer which are in the knowledge of many and are commonly known to others cannot be called as trade secrets.⁴⁰

Garden Leave Clause

Garden Leave is the practice whereby an employee leaving a job is instructed to stay away from work during the notice period, while still remaining on the payroll.⁴¹ Garden Leave clause that operates after the term of employment has been held as restraint of trade and therefore hit by Section 27 of The Contract Act. The Bombay High Court held that the payment of compensation under Garden Leave Clause does not renew the contract of employment which has come to an end. The Garden Leave Clause is therefore, prima facie in restraint of trade and is hit by Section 27 of the Contract Act.⁴²

³⁸ VFS Global Services (P) Ltd. v. Suprit Roy, (2008) 3 Mah LJ 266.

³⁹ Star India Private Ltd v. LaxmirajSeetharamNayak and Anr. 2003 (3) Maha LJ 726.

⁴⁰ Ambiance India (P) Ltd. v. Naveen Jain, (2005) 81 DRJ 538.

⁴¹ Wikipedia.org, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Garden_leave (last visited Dec. 5, 2022).

⁴² VFS Global Services (P) Ltd. v. Suprit Roy, (2008) 3 Mah LJ 266.

However, when as per the clause, the employee was required to give a three-month notice prior to the cessation of employment, which would in effect function as a garden leave period, the Delhi High Court upheld the validity of such a clause.⁴³

Conclusion

It can be concluded that the Courts have frowned upon restraints which tie employees after the period of employment is over. Covenant to serve an employer exclusively during the term of employment is not hit by Section 27 of The Contract Act. An enquiry into whether the restraint is merely partial or complete or reasonable or unreasonable is not envisaged by Section 27 of the Contract Act unless it falls within the purview of exception carved out in the aforesaid section. Courts take a stricter view and resort to careful scrutiny while interpreting employee-employer contracts, by keeping in mind the inequality of bargaining power between an employer and employee. An Employer is entitled to recover reasonable damages when an employee after receiving training from an employer leaves the job prior to the termination of the stipulated employment period.

Further, as held by various High Courts employers can restrain employees from divulging trade secrets even after the determination of employment period. Similarly, covenants that relate to non-solicitation operate even after the termination of employment contract unless such covenants are unreasonable. Garden leave clauses that seek to operate after the determination of employment contract are hit by Section 27 of the Contract Act and, therefore, not valid.

The doctrine of restraint of trade is not confined to contracts of employment, but is also applicable to all other contracts.⁴⁴

⁴³ Kailash Kumar v. Syndicate Bank Ltd, 2018IAD(Delhi)444.

⁴⁴ Percept D'Mark (India) Pvt. Ltd. v. Zaheer Khan, (2006) 4 SCC 227.

LAW & JUSTICE IN GLOBALIZING WORLD THE MOVEMENT OF CRIMINAL LAW TOWARDS EQUALITY AND JUSTICE FOR ALL REGARDLESS OF GENDER

Megha Chadha*

Abstract

The binary notion of the term “gender” is strongly ingrained in society’s mentality, however the term’s true meaning is that it encompasses male, female, and transgender people. Laws that are gender-neutral aim to treat all genders equally and without harmful prejudice in terms of punishment and opportunity. Since the mediaeval era in Indian history, weak women have been oppressed and exploited; as a result, laws have been passed to grant them specific protection. Women are now on a level with men in terms of status, education, and employment thanks to the sincere efforts of legislators, But since the advent of globalisation, the term feminism is misunderstood. With the ongoing development of the socio-legal system, the rights of these other communities must also be acknowledged. This essay focuses on the disparities between India’s many gender-specific criminal laws, particularly those that pertain to sexual offences and cruelty, and the rights to justice, liberty, equality, and dignity that our Constitution guarantees. Changing gender-biased criminal legislation is necessary because to focus on uplifting women is not to discount the plight of other marginalised people. Concerns about sexual orientation, gender identity, and gender-based discrimination are only some of the issues that are raised in this article and need to be handled before gender-neutral legislation may be implemented.

I. INTRODUCTION

We have a skewed picture of gender roles because of harmful

stereotypes, such as the idea transgender people are the impoverished, women can only be carers, and males can only provide for their families. As a result of these ideologies, the bulk of Indian law is biased toward one gender or the other; for example, Indian family law is based on patriarchal, patrilineal, and patrilocal values.¹ When it comes to “sexual offences” and “cruelty”, the criminal laws of the country assign males the position of offender and females the role of victim, but transgender persons are not assigned to either role. Legislators have never considered enacting gender-neutral laws since, in their view, sexual assaults on women are by far the most common type of sexual crime. When the rights of one minority group are disregarded in order to ostensibly protect the rights of another minority group, a violation of justice occurs on both a moral and legal level.

II. PROVISION OF CONSTITUTION

The Preamble of our Constitution states that its inhabitants would be guaranteed “social, economic, and political justice” as well as “equality of position and opportunity.”² Fundamental Rights have transformed this promise into a guarantee. All people are granted equality in one way or another under Articles 14, 15, and 16³. This means that Article 14 may be compared to a genus, while Articles 15 and 16 can be compared to species. According to Article 14, “the State shall not deny anybody equality before the law or the equal protection of the laws” and This rule also subtly incorporates the idea of “equality among equals” or justifiable categorisation. Citizens are protected from discrimination under Article 15 of the Constitution, including sex-based discrimination. As an exception

¹ Flavia Agnes, *India's Family Laws Are Discriminatory. That's Why Judges Shouldn't Be "Neutral" on Gender.*, THE WIRE, <https://thewire.in/women/indias-family-laws-are-gender-blind-judges-shouldnt-be-afraid-to-question-them> (last visited Jan 22, 2023).

² INDIA CONST. Preamble.

³ INDIA CONST. Art. 14, 15, 16.

to Articles 14 and 15(1) and (2), Article 15(3)⁴ allows the state to make any exceptional provisions it sees fit for the “benefit of women and children.” The main goals were to increase women’s influence and close the gender inequity gap.

III. IMPORTANT LAWS THAT ARE GENDER-SPECIFIC

- **§ 498-A of “Indian Penal Code”⁵**

The violation of § 498-A is a cognizable offence that cannot be compounded or subject to bail. Thus, it established the accused’s guilt before it was proven, which goes against natural justice principles that state that an accused person is assumed innocent until proven guilty. The Criminal Procedure Code’s Section 41⁶ gives the police broad authority to detain the accused without a warrant. Most often, when a cognizable offence occurs, the police, paralysed by the idea of women’s maltreatment, act hastily and without consideration. Protection for abused women is necessary, but Putting the accused spouse and his family in detention facilities or keeping them there until a court gives them bail is not an acceptable way to provide them with such protection. The abuse of the section has progressed to the point where the police are even requesting payments from the spouse or his family members.

There is no question that women have abused this clause in a huge number of instances, but that does not imply it has lost its fundamental standing. It is categorically false to suggest that such forms of cruelty are only naturally associated with men because the word “abuse” encompasses physical, mental, as well as emotional cruelty. Any gender can become entangled in the victimisation web, and our laws must provide equal protection for everyone.

⁴ *INDIA CONST.* Art. 15, cl. 1, 2 and 3.

⁵ The Indian Penal Code, 1860, No. 45, Acts of Parliament, 1860, § 498A (India).

⁶ The Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973, No. 2, Acts of Parliament, 1974, § 41 (India).

- **Provision under “Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005”**

The legislature passed “the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005”⁷ to fill in the legal deficiencies in §498-A IPC. This Act expanded the definition of domestic violence and gives female victims of the crime access to both civil and criminal legal remedies, including protection orders and injunctions in their favour. An important distinction is that the PWDVA extends the remedy to victims of “domestic relationships,” which includes “any ties based on consanguinity, marriage, adoption, and even partnerships which were in the nature of marriage.”

Due to the assumption that men commit the majority of crimes, this Act is also hampered by gender sensitivity. Because of this, the persecution of transgender persons has not been acknowledged in PWDVA, and the “aggrieved person” is clearly the “woman.” Due to institutional shortcomings, both the PWDVA and section 498A of the IPC have shown to be ineffectual in the majority of instances.

- **Sexual offences such as rape**

The most infamous Nirbhaya case prompted significant changes to the definition of rape and the addition of multiple additional sexual offences to the Indian Penal Code. According to the idea of rape as it has developed, a man may penetrate a woman’s mouth, urethra, anus, or any other area of her body using any item or portion of his body. The only application used to be penile-vaginal penetration. Our gender-specific laws serve as the best illustration of how deeply ingrained the concepts of masculine dominance and feminine sensibility are in our culture. Unfortunately, court rulings on the rape laws in India also show a fairly traditional conception of the crime, where rape is seen as an assault on a woman’s body in addition to her modesty, chastity, and honour. The efficacy of

⁷ The Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, No. 43, Acts of Parliament, 2005 (India).

defences is weakened by this patriarchal perspective. The right to a dignified existence, which includes the right to one's own body, is becoming more and more linked to rape. Any age or sexual orientation can lead to a sexual assault. The rationale that male, female, or transgender criminals or victims may be involved in rape and other sexual offences should be included into the law. The lady in a rape case is deemed to not have provided permission if she declares as much in court, in accordance with section 114A of the Indian Evidence Act.⁸ On the other hand, other elements of society are not adequately protected by our laws against sexual offences. It flagrantly entails a grave infringement of the right to equality. Despite the fact that Indian law does not classify marital rape as rape, consensual sex that is performed when a couple is pretending to be married is frequently seen as rape. As a result, the legislation as a whole becomes highly lopsided.

- **Other Sexual Offences under IPC**

According to §354-A,⁹ males who violate any of the provisions of the law against women—including physical contact, the demand or solicitation for sexual favours, statements with sexual overtones, the exhibition of pornography without their will—are liable to fines and/or jail as punishment. Similar to this, it has been established that voyeurism and stalking are crimes committed by men against women under sections 354C and D¹⁰, respectively. This was made public after Vijay Nair, a music businessman, discovered he had no legal options after a lady pursued him repeatedly online. These discriminatory laws against women not only violate the standards of justice and equality but also make a mockery of human rights.

- **Justice Verma Committee Report**

A report by the Justice Verma Committee was released in 2013 in

⁸ The Indian Evidence Act, 1872, No. 1, Acts of Parliament, 1872, § 114A (India).

⁹ The Indian Penal Code, 1860, No. 45, Acts of Parliament, 1860, § 354A (India).¹⁰ Ibid, § 354B, 354C (India)

response to the Nirbhaya Case, making recommendations for reforms to existing rape legislation. The Committee has recognised “the right to sexual orientation” as human right, i.e., India cannot deny its inhabitants the “right to be different.” Without a doubt, the Committee was in favour of homosexual and transgender people’s rights being covered by laws that protect individuals from crimes like “sexual assault and harassment.” The Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2013,¹¹ disregarded these suggestions, rendering the Committee’s work useless. The Committee further stated that since children at this age do not understand concepts like “gender,” “masculinity,” “feminism,” it is the responsibility of adults to educate them about concepts other than “perceived notions” by, for example, “stripping out the language of sexism from books/materials, eliminating different lessons for girls and boys (i.e. sewing vs. sports)”. As a result, the Committee illustrated how important personal and sexual education is for fostering a more gender-neutral social environment in youngsters.

- **Bill on Gender Neutral Laws, 2019**

In the matter of “Criminal Justice Society of India v. Union of India”¹², the Apex Court dismissed the plea made by an NGO stating that, “The Parliament has to make a call on the subject.” Then, in July 2019, the bill was proposed to “make sexual offence legislation gender-neutral” by prominent attorney and legislator KTS Tulsi in the Rajya Sabha. To guarantee that the phrases “any man” and “any woman” in the portions of the laws dealing to sexual offences be modified to read “any person,” the bill suggested amending “the Indian Penal Code,” “the Criminal Procedure Code,” and “the Indian Evidence Act.” The bill also requests that Section 375A of the IPC be included to criminalise “sexual assault,” which is defined as “intentionally touching the genitals,

¹¹ The Criminal Law Amendment Act, 2013, No. 13, Acts of Parliament, 2013 (India).

¹² AIR 2010 Del 194.

anus, or breast of the person” or “forcing the person to intentionally touch the vagina, penis, anus, or breast of that person or any other person without that person’s consent, except where such touching is done for proper hygienic or medical purposes.” These planned revisions were quickly abandoned because of the central government’s strong opposition on the grounds that the statistics significantly favour the justification of regulations that only apply to women. Compared to sexual assault against males or transgender people, sexual assault against women is significantly more targeted. Men’s sexual assault is a subject that is rarely mentioned, and when it is, it usually has a humorous undertone. By decriminalising adultery, the Supreme Court took the initiative to introduce neutrality to laws that are gender sensitive. Unfortunately, the government’s precarious stance against gender equality appears to run counter to the Supreme Court of India’s proactive approach.

- **Rights of Transgenders**

When the British implemented “the Criminal Tribes Act, 1871”¹³ which was specifically directed towards them, the standing of the community of third gender people began to decline. Transgender people were treated as felons under this law and could not be released on bond. They might be detained without a warrant, sentenced to up to two years in jail, fined, or both. Even though the Act was abolished in 1952, the harm it did is still evident. The first law to specifically criminalise transgender people is §377 of the IPC¹⁴, which defines unnatural sexual activity as a crime punishable by up to 10 years in jail or life in prison.

The Supreme Court demonstrated tolerance and compassion for transgender people in the precedent-setting case of “National Legal

¹³ Criminal Tribes Act, 1871, No. 27, Acts of Parliament, 1871 (India).

¹⁴ The Indian Penal Code, 1860, No. 45, Acts of Parliament, 1860, § 377 (India).

Services Authority v. Union of India”¹⁵. Since transgender people & Hijras are not given equal legal protection under the law, they frequently experience prejudice. Transgender people must be acknowledged as “third persons.” The third community gender is included in the definition of “persons” or “citizens” as specified in the Constitution, according to the country’s legal interpretation. According to the SC, transgender people also have the right to the protections provided by Articles 14, 15, 16, 19, and 21¹⁶. As a result, the focus has shifted from worries about charity or sympathy to human rights. The Supreme Court also gave orders to take steps to reserve seats for people of the third gender in educational institutions and public employment, as well as to take appropriate action to ensure that transgender patients receive proper medical care in hospitals and have access to “separate public restrooms” and other facilities. The Court understood that transgender people’s fears of public humiliation are linked to the general public’s failure to grasp the concept of gender fluidity. Both Governments have been tasked with raising public knowledge of third gender people so that they are not seen as an isolated group but rather as an integral part of society. As a result, different government actions should be done for the welfare and advancement of third gender people. Thus, it had ordered national and state governments to conduct education and outreach initiatives and take transgender people’s fears, embarrassment, gender dysphoria, peer pressure, depression, suicide thoughts, and other difficulties seriously.

The “Standing Committee on Social Justice and Empowerment” was established in July, 2017 to analyse the “Transgender Bill.” In its report, the committee noted a number of issues with the final text and made recommendations. Despite the numerous objections contained in the Standing Committee Report, the Committee’s amendments and suggestions were not included in the Bill when it

¹⁵ AIR 2015 SC 1863.

¹⁶ *INDIA CONST.* Art. 14, 15, 16, 19 & 21.

was tabled in Parliament. The transgender community refers to August 5, 2019, the day “The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Bill” was approved by the Lok Sabha, as “Gender Justice Murder Day.”¹⁷ It’s not even a toothless tiger; there are just a few teeth, and they’re all over the place and lack the motivation, authority, or capability to act on their own. The maximum sentence for any offence committed against transgender people, including sexual assault and endangering life, is two years. In contrast to the Indian Penal Code, minor punishments are imposed on offenders who commit serious crimes.

IV. COMPARATIVE STUDY WITH OTHER NATIONS

- USA

In American law, the word “rape” is not used. According to Chapter 109 A of the United States Code, rape includes all non-consensual sexual activities. Since the term “anyone” is used in the terms of the sexual abuse legislation, they are not gender-specific. The definition of “intimate partner” is broadened to include both men and women in domestic violence laws from several states, including “California, New York, and Washington, D.C.”

- UK

The Sexual Offences Act, 2003, which governs rape legislation in the UK, provides a definition of rape that denotes a man as the preparator, but section 3’s term of “sexual assault” is gender-neutral and essentially embraces any touching that is sexual in nature. The 1997 Protection from Harassment Act is gender neutral since it states that “A person shall not pursue a code of behaviour which amounts to harassing the other.” Additionally, patterns of coercive or controlling behaviour when used against a family member or intimate partner are illegal.

¹⁷ Prachi Singh, *Why is transgender community unhappy with Trans Persons Bill?*, DOWN TO EARTH, <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/blog/governance/why-is-transgender-community-unhappy-with-trans-persons-bill—67158> (last visited Jan 22, 2023).

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The law must be steady but it must not stagnate, according to Roscoe Pound. As a result, the law need to be flexible and a model of equality and fairness. Improving women's status should not mean ignoring the plight of victims in other groups, hence gender-biased criminal legislation must be changed. The moment is right for Indian law to consider whether gender-specific laws are fostering gender inequality rather than promoting gender parity because so many developed and developing nations have adopted gender neutrality. People of all genders have the right to be free from sexual assault, and the phrase "human being" encompasses all individuals. The time has come to move away from gender-specific approaches and toward gender-neutral ones. Ultimately, the goal of gender neutrality is to build a society in which all people, regardless of their gender identity, are treated equally. Men are most definitely not the devilish figures and women are not the saintly beings who have the exclusive right to victimisation. The reality of male victimisation, female criminalization, and transgender inclusion must be examined, incorporated, and applied to our laws. It is also advised to use gender-neutral vocabulary, such as saying "any person" or "any spouse" instead of "any man" or "any woman," or "husband" and "wife," respectively. All offenders and victims should be treated equally under the Constitution's conception of equality. It is necessary to broaden the definition of rape in order to recognise both homosexual rape and marital rape. In circumstances involving rape by a group or the abetting of rape, the female member must also face consequences. Male and transgender victims of domestic violence should be included in the preparations for the "Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005" and the "Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redress) Act, 2013," and the laws should be revised to provide clearer guidelines and procedures for conclusively determining the guilt of the accused.

Until profoundly rooted masculine domination is removed from

society, gender-neutral laws will not work. Children must also be raised in a gender-neutral atmosphere, free from gender preconceptions such as “boys don’t cry,” “women belong in the kitchen,” and others, taking into account the effect of education and perception. It may thus be claimed that gender neutrality and educational success are inextricably related, and that parents must initiate it at the family level in the home.

Before the lack of gender neutrality is addressed, more effective application of women’s protection legislation must be made so that women may genuinely stand on an equal footing with men. Finally, all genders must be socially and legally recognised before gender non-biasness is introduced. Even though The Transgender Persons (Protection of Rights) Act of 2019 gave transgender people legal recognition, they continue to be ridiculed and lack protection under our criminal laws. Finally, it’s important to keep in mind that true equality means holding everyone to the same standards of accountability.

IILM Law Journal (IILMLJ)
Volume I, Issue No. 1, 2023
Maiden Issue
Declaration

S.No.	Particulars	Details
1	Place of publication	Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh
2	Periodicity	Biannual
3	Language	English only
4	Editor	Prof. M. Afzal Wani
5	Owner, Publisher & Printer	IILM University, Knowledge Park-II, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306

TRUTH OF THESE PARTICULARS IS
CERTIFIED BY THE EDITOR

IILM School of Law, IILM University, Knowledge Park-II,
Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306

About the Journal

IILM Law Journal (IILMLJ) is a *peer reviewed journal* of the IILM School of Law, IILM University, Knowledge Park-II, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh-201306 at a distance of just 30 km from the Supreme Court of India connected by Noida Express Way. With an open airy location and delightful sentinel building, amidst the faculties of technology, management and liberal arts, its main feature is a holistic academic atmosphere in interdisciplinary settings. Students have an opportunity to excel to meet professional requirement at all possible levels. Experiential learning at the core of the academic programming with finely defined outcome. The present journal is a humble attempt to proceed ahead with the hope of developing best research and writing skills.

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Font; Times New Roman

Font size: 12 points for text and 10 points for foot notes.

Spacing: 1.5

Quotations: Indented towards right

Mode of Submission: Email

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